

Artificial Neural Networks for Bio-based Chemical Production or Biorefining: A Review

Brett Pomeroy^a, Miha Grilc^a, Blaž Likozar^{a,*}

^a *Department of Catalysis and Chemical Reaction Engineering, National Institute of Chemistry,
Hajdrihova 19, 1000 Ljubljana, Slovenia*

ARTICLE INFO

Word count (19,318 words)

* Corresponding author. Tel.: +386 1 4760 281; fax: +386 1 4760300.

E-mail address: blaz.likozar@ki.si (B. Likozar).

Contents

<i>Abstract</i>	3
<i>Keywords:</i>	3
<i>1. Introduction: Bio-based Chemical Production through Biorefining</i>	5
<i>2. Biorefining Modelling through Mechanistic Approaches</i>	8
2.1 <i>Pyrolysis</i>	9
2.2 <i>Combustion</i>	10
2.3 <i>Enzymatic Hydrolysis</i>	11
2.4 <i>Fermentation and Anaerobic Digestion</i>	12
<i>3. Artificial Neural Networks and its Use in Fossil Fuel Conversion</i>	13
3.1 <i>Fischer-Tropsch Synthesis</i>	20
3.2 <i>Hydrodesulfurization and Hydrotreatment</i>	20
3.3 <i>Crude Oil Distillation and Bubble Point Pressure</i>	21
3.4 <i>Steam Reforming, Methanol Production, and Dehydrogenation</i>	21
<i>4. Machine Learning Implementation for Biorefinery Optimization</i>	22
4.1 <i>Thermochemical Processes</i>	26
4.1.1 <i>Gasification</i>	26
4.1.2 <i>Pyrolysis</i>	26
4.1.3 <i>Thermal Properties</i>	29
4.2 <i>Chemical Processes</i>	31
4.2.1 <i>Transesterification</i>	31
4.2.2 <i>Hydrolysis</i>	32
4.3 <i>Biochemical Processes</i>	36
4.3.1 <i>Fermentation</i>	36
4.3.2 <i>Anaerobic Digestion</i>	37
<i>5. Modelling for Simulations, Intensification & Control</i>	38
<i>6. Conclusions and Outlook</i>	41
<i>Acknowledgments</i>	44
<i>References</i>	44

Abstract

Artificial neural networks have emerged as vital tools to predict chemical behavior for many of the most recognized biomass valorization processes relevant to biorefineries for the purpose of optimization of desired products and reaction conditions. Until recently, these neural network methodologies have successfully been utilized in the petroleum industry where much more extensive databases are available for effective algorithm training. These systems provide compelling advantages for pattern recognition when interpreting the influence of ever-changing feedstock compositions for complex biomass conversion processes as they do not require any a priori knowledge of reaction mechanisms or thermodynamic phenomena. This has been revealed to be tremendously beneficial for real-time, dynamic control applications of biochemical processes for rapid parameter monitoring and regulation such as during fermentation or anaerobic digestion. This review aims to present and evaluate studies that have attempted to apply these neural network strategies to various aspects of biorefining and how these models address the common challenges that occur when relying on conventional mechanistic modelling approaches to estimate sophisticated, non-linear systems. Comparisons are then identified when implementing these artificial intelligence computing practices in traditional petroleum refineries where feedstock inconsistencies are not as paramount compared to biorefineries. Subsequently, the practicality of these neural networks is critically assessed and recommendations are presented on how to strengthen its applicability and predictability towards future bio-based chemical production. Mathematical models such as artificial neural networks will be an integral technology in the future bioeconomy for the realization of innovative biorefinery concepts as computational power continues to advance.

Keywords:

Biorefinery;

Biomass Valorization;

Machine Learning;

Artificial Neural Networks;

Process Control;

Optimization;

Notations and nomenclature	
AI	Artificial intelligence
ANN	Artificial neural networks
ANFIS	Adaptive neuro fuzzy inference system
FL	Fuzzy logic
BPFANN	Back propagation feed forward artificial neural networks
RSM	Response surface methodology
OVAT	One variable at a time
DoE	Design of experiments
FT	Fischer-Tropsch
HHV	Higher heating value
HDS	Hydrodesulfurization
PSO	Particle swarm optimization
GA	Genetic algorithm
R^2	Correlation coefficient
MSE	Mean square error
RMSE	Relative mean square error
MAE	Mean absolute error
MAPE	Mean absolute percentage error

1. Introduction: Bio-based Chemical Production through Biorefining

Currently, the vast majority of chemicals and fuels are produced from fossil fuels such as oil and natural gas, in a typical crude oil refinery system that is generally inefficient and environmentally harmful (in terms of waste products and greenhouse gas emissions) and depends on unsustainable feedstocks. There is an urgent need to develop more sustainable methods that rely on renewable resources such as biomass to fulfill our global energy and chemical needs. There is approximately 170 billion tonnes of biomass annually produced and only around 3-4% is currently exploited [1]. Thus, there is an enormous amount of biomass available for its valorization as a raw material to obtain biofuels and other valuable chemical products.

Biorefining is the approach of sustainable biomass processing to produce bio-based products and energy as economical, cost-effective, and efficient as possible. The biorefinery concept is a vital part of the modern circular economy to reduce as much waste as possible while simultaneously producing several value-added chemical products and/or biofuels. A brief comparison between a traditional petroleum refinery and a biorefinery is illustrated in Table 1. Biorefineries are partially analogous to the traditional petroleum refineries that have been a pinnacle provider to our current global energy needs for over 100 years. The key difference between petroleum refineries and biorefineries is the feedstock, in which the latter employs biomass as a renewable resource in the attempt to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and waste generation which will be essential for a more sustainable future.

Table 1: Comparison between a traditional petroleum refinery and a biorefinery

Petroleum Refinery	Biorefinery
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Consistent feedstock composition• Negligible oxygen content• Moderate sulfur content• Relatively high feedstock cost• Non-renewable	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Greatly fluctuating feedstock composition• High oxygen content• Low sulfur content• Cheap feedstock cost (lignocellulosic biomass)• Renewable

A major emphasis for biorefineries is on the greatest economic value that is sustainable and a closed, circular life cycle with zero waste. These two factors will enable the feasibility of biorefineries to be more competitive relative to the old-fashioned but established petroleum refineries. Thus far, most biorefinery concepts involve mainly drop-in biofuel production (high production, low value) from biomass while concurrently using unexploited revenue streams to co-produce more valuable bio-based chemical products [2]. Until recently, biomass has generally been used only for energy production in terms of heat to be recirculated back into industrial processes which greatly underutilizes its economic potential. Although not completely waste free, biorefineries are much more integrated systems relative to their traditional petroleum counterparts which attempts to utilize all resource streams, allowing processes to be more marketable with the possibility to supplement additional environmental factors [3].

Three main generations or phases of biorefineries have been commonly described in the literature which vary depending on feedstock, process, and products. Phase I biorefinery involve only one feedstock to produce a single major project. Similarly, phase II biorefinery uses only 1 feedstock but expands to multiple processes leading to more than one major product. The most desirable and versatile type, phase III biorefineries can handle multiple feedstocks via several different processes to produce many different major products [4][5]. These phases can be further separated into several subtypes of biorefineries based on more

specifics, although a precise classification remains disputed due to the rather daunting number of possibilities [6][7]. Biomass feedstocks include agricultural crops or residues such as lignocellulosic crops, grasses, oil crops, sugar crops, starch crops, forestry crops and their residues, and marine biomass such as algae. Industrial and domestic wastes have also been investigated [8].

With respect to petroleum refineries, crude oil as a feedstock has negligible oxygen content, rich in hydrocarbons, moderate sulfur, and is relatively consistent in terms of composition and availability which simplifies its conversion to platform chemicals. Alternatively, biomass has negligible sulfur but a much greater content of oxygen, and its composition can vary considerably between sources [9]. A biorefinery also must often operate in a seasonal timeframe unlike fossil fuels, further complicating its operation. This high oxygen content provides several intrinsic properties including lower heating capacity, increased polarity, and also increased reactivity compared to fossil fuel resources. Although, this oxygen also provides a much richer pool of functional groups that permits the formation of an immense range of products that are not plausible or economically feasible to produce from fossil fuel resources.

Many technological processes are required to convert the raw biomass feedstock to an actual worthwhile chemical or biofuel. A depiction of the potential processing routes that can be applied within a biofinery concept utilizing various lignocellulosic biomass feedstocks is presented in Figure 1. There are several review papers that have thoroughly described these conversion processes in much more detail; thermochemical [10][11], biochemical [12][13], chemical [14] [15]. Typically, processes are reported into three main subgroups [16];

- 1) Thermochemical processes to convert biomass into chemicals and/or fuels are generally performed by thermal decomposition under rather harsh temperature and pressure conditions. Pyrolysis and gasification are the two main methods that convert biomass to bio-oil and syngas, respectively. Combustion, although a rather rudimentary process nowadays, is also considered a thermochemical process but ultimately only produces heat for energy.
- 2) Chemical processes alter the chemical structure of the biomass through chemical reactions with added co-reactants and catalysts. The most common routes include hydrolysis to depolymerize polysaccharides and proteins into their distinctive building blocks, and transesterification of vegetable (or animal) oils to form fatty acids in the form of biodiesel.
- 3) Biochemical processes, unlike thermochemical, generally occur under mild temperatures and lower reaction rates. Fermentation of sugars and other fermentable feedstocks via enzymes or microorganisms to produce alcohols (bioethanol) and other value-added chemical products is a highly prospective biochemical process. Anaerobic digestion of wastes and residues to form biogas (CO₂, methane mostly) has also been demonstrated to have great potential.

Figure 1: Possible biorefinery processing routes from lignocellulosic biomass feedstocks. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [6]. Copyright 2009 John Wiley and Sons.

There are over 200 biorefineries currently in operation in Europe, however, the vast majority are considered unsatisfactory and unsustainable “first-generation” facilities which utilize sugar and starch feedstocks which competes with food and animal feed crops [17]. To be more efficient and maximize economical potential, new generation biorefineries that depend on lignocellulosic biomasses must combine several overlapping processes that can cope with many different feedstocks, while minimizing waste streams as much as possible, what are known as integrated biorefineries [18][19]. However, this generates very complex process situations, especially when relying on solely experimental techniques to explore potential biorefinery systems (Figure 1). This inherent complexity also provokes major challenges when attempting to upscale biorefineries from lab-scale to an industrial level, the simulation of new reactor configurations under genuine reaction conditions, and the optimization of process or unit operations. Therefore, it is essential to develop inexpensive and effective methods to gain a more in-depth understanding of these intricate systems to ease their operation. The implementation of computational models for this purpose has newly thrived for applications in the development and simulation of biorefinery conceptions as computational power and software has significantly expanded in the 21st century. Computational techniques

allow a quick and cost-effective way to accurately and proficiently predict chemical behaviours and reaction phenomena which are impractical or even impossible to attain through solely experimental or theoretical means. Computational modeling is still in the early stages of advancement, though evidence thus far strongly reveals its immense potential as a useful and worthwhile tool for chemical engineering disciplines. Specifically, artificial neural networks (ANN) have recently emerged as effective, prognostic modelling systems that could have enormous potential within biorefineries to better understand and cope with the inconsistent and unreliable feedstocks. A few literature reviews have been published that highlight the application of ANN models for sustainable development [20], biodiesel production [21][22], microbial biofuel production [23], pyrolysis [24], and prediction of biomass thermal properties and HHV [25][26] [27], although they are all limited by only focusing on one specific aspect within a biorefinery concept. Therefore, this novel work aims to review and critically assess studies that have applied ANN systems for a wider range of biomass conversion processes relevant to many different potential biorefinery schemes. First, a brief overview of modelling through mechanistic approaches is presented which showcases their use and limitations for the purpose of bio-based chemical production. Next, examples are presented in which neural networks have been successfully employed in the petroleum industry for different fossil fuel conversion processes, demonstrating their potential as a predictive tool when sufficient large data sets are available. Finally, a comprehensive review of the literature is described and evaluated which elucidates the applicability of ANN modelling for optimization and process control within a biorefinery approach when inconsistent feedstocks are involved. Recommendations and future outlook are brought forth on how to improve the predictability and usefulness of such modelling practices to become a vital tool for the implementation of novel biomass conversion processes.

2. Biorefining Modelling through Mechanistic Approaches

Mathematical modelling techniques can be applied to several different stages of a biorefinery including initial proof-of-concepts and demonstrational bench-top level for upscaling purposes, reactor design, as well as entire commercial plants for process intensification and optimization. This can be very advantageous by reducing the need for expensive and often time consuming experimentation when handling frequently shifting biomass feedstocks and compositions, especially on a large industrial scale [28][29]. Related to chemical engineering, a mechanistic model is composed of mathematical equations that explain the internal operations of a system in terms of its individual parts and mechanisms. Mechanistic models are based on deterministic principles which stipulate that given the initial conditions of a system, future behaviour can be accurately predicted, presuming that the system is accurately represented by the actions of its individual constituents. Mechanistic models for biorefinery processes are developed based on mass, heat and momentum balances, accompanied with appropriate mechanism formulations (e.g. reaction kinetic expressions to replicate process dynamics) [30]. Mechanistic models can be vital tools for studying the reaction kinetics and mechanisms of complex reaction systems such as those regarding the degradation of biomass. The following examples are a very brief description of a small sample of available studies that have implemented mechanistic modelling systems for the purpose of elucidating the complexities that transpire during biomass conversion processes. They aim is to demonstrate the immense knowledge and insight that is necessary for their development which must consider the presence of sometimes hundreds of distinct reactions and intermediates, in addition to sophisticated heat and mass transfer correlations.

2.1 Pyrolysis

A mechanistic model for fast pyrolysis is quite challenging due to the extreme heating rates ($>1000\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C s}^{-1}$) and very short residence times, making determining precise reaction mechanisms and the lengthy number of intermediates by exclusively experimental methods very problematic. Attempts have been made to construct an accurate, realistic mechanistic model for the fast pyrolysis of cellulose and other glucose-based compounds to predict dominant products across the millisecond timescale. Vinu et al. reported an exceptional mechanistic model for fast pyrolysis of cellulose and other glucose-based carbohydrates that estimated conversion and formation of intermediates and products over the brief timescale [31]. All rate parameters applied in the kinetic model including activation energies and frequency factors were acquired mostly from experimental or quantum chemical calculations from the literature. The model considered the formation of all possible C1-C6 organic products during fast pyrolysis of cellulose which involved an astonishing 99 individual reactions. A small portion of the reactions are displayed in Figure 2. The established model was then tested for related glucose-based carbohydrates such as cellobiose and glucose and then compared to published experimental data with sufficient accuracy.

Figure 2: A portion of the numerous reaction mechanisms possible from the pyrolysis of glucose. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [31]. Copyright 2012 The Royal Society of Chemistry.

Zhou et al. also developed a computational framework for a mechanistic model of fast pyrolysis of cellulose based on experimental data collected from a micro-pyrolyzer fitted with GC-MS/FID [32][33]. The model, which included 342 distinct reactions and 103 species, was then validated with good agreement for major gas and liquid product yields that were detected experimentally. The time evolution of desired products was also able to be accurately predicted during the reaction over the course of just a few seconds, as shown in Figure 3. Similarly, a mechanistic model for hemicellulose was reported based on experimental decomposition mechanisms, which once again included a tremendous 504 individual reactions of 114 species [34]. We would like to refer to a complete review on biomass pyrolysis mechanistic models which has been published elsewhere for a list of more relevant examples [35].

Figure 3: Time evolution of the main products during the pyrolysis of cellulose. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [33]. Copyright 2014 American Chemical Society.

2.2 Combustion

Mechanistic models have been presented for the combustion of biomass, although the intricate phenomena involved during combustion results in an incredibly complex system with several dynamic components. Nevertheless, mechanistic modelling is often the preferred method which can guarantee adequate accuracy since non-linear system identification can sometimes suffer from several shortcomings [36]. Boriouchkine et al. have attempted to simplify such biomass combustion models to describe only relevant phenomena and behaviour by considering reaction rates, and heat and mass transfer mechanisms amongst both gas and solid phases of a biomass grate boiler furnace [36]. An outline of their “simplified” model is presented in Figure 4 in which they validated with industrial experimental data with relatively good agreement.

Figure 4: Overview of a simplified mechanistic model for biomass combustion. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [36]. Copyright 2010 Elsevier Ltd.

2.3 Enzymatic Hydrolysis

Mechanistic modeling offers several advantages over empirical kinetic models for enzymatic hydrolysis as it can provide a much more in-depth understanding of chemical and/or physical behavior of the dynamic biological system [37]. Enzymatic cellulose hydrolysis has emerged as an effective method to break up cellulose into smaller, more workable sub-units and although the process seems relatively simple at first glance which encompasses only cleavage of bonds, many unknowns remain regarding exact mechanisms and related kinetics. Interactions between the cellulose substrates and enzymes involves several steps including adsorption and complexation results in an intricate dynamic system [38]. Several groups have proposed mechanistic models to investigate this process with varying success [39]. For example, a mechanistic model of enzymatic hydrolysis of cellulose was proposed by Huron et al. that considers the morphology of substrates such as cellulose particle length and radius, and hydrolysis mechanisms using four key cellulase enzymes [40]. Based on experimental data obtained in the literature, validation tests for the model demonstrated remarkable agreement and provided valuable insights into hydrolysis rates that is dependent on intrinsic cellulose structural characteristics that were generally neglected in other modelling approaches. Others have also developed a model to predict chain length of cellulose polymers and sugars

during depolymerization (chain-end scission) hydrolysis based on quasi-Monte-Carlo and validated against experimental data for optimization purposes [41][42].

2.4 Fermentation and Anaerobic Digestion

Mechanistic models can be a valuable technique to understand the dynamic environment of fermentation and has been utilized for several components regarding process development and operation [43]. Due to the fact that biological processes are quite multifaceted and complicated systems, specific phenomena are not completely understood enough to be modelled precisely using solely deterministic models. Therefore, often mechanistic models for fermentation consist of first-principle fundamentals of physical behaviours combined with empirical data for metabolic rates and growth kinetics [30]. A schematic of the typical steps involved in the mechanistic modelling and simulation of biomass fermentation is shown in Figure 5 which are rather labour intensive. Anaerobic digestion can also be a difficult process to determine accurate kinetics and mechanisms as it involves several dynamic multi-steps requiring various types of bacterium with differing metabolic reactions. Until recently, empirical methods have been mainly employed for the design and scale-up of anaerobic digesters, although are often expensive and time-consuming approaches. Mechanistic models that consider biochemical and physicochemical phenomena have been reported but accurate constants are limited and typically are bacteria dependent. For example, Yu et al. described a mechanistic model, based on universally agreed pathways, for anaerobic digestion of bio-based wastes for the production of biogas which implemented complex microbial kinetics, transport phenomena, and stoichiometric relationships [44].

Figure 5: General mechanistic model schematic fitted with experimental analysis for fermentation of biomass. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [30]. Copyright 2010 Elsevier Ltd.

3. Artificial Neural Networks and its Use in Fossil Fuel Conversion

Mechanistic models can offer vital information related to reaction mechanisms, however, several shortcomings for their effective implementation remain. It is clear from the previous examples, due to the immense complexity of reactions and intrinsic physical transport phenomena of biomass conversion processes, mechanistic models require a substantial amount of computational time and resources to be effective. Limitations of currently available experimental techniques as well as extensive computational power for the management and analysis of these data also further hinders this work. This intrinsic complexity is generally not necessary for the optimization or regulation of a specific process to maximize yields or minimize energy consumption. A potential modelling technique that addresses these challenges is the use of artificial neural networks (ANN). ANN are particularly useful in system modelling such as in complex mappings and system identification, and are much simpler and user friendly compared to first-principle models which do not require as much programming or mathematical proficiencies to convey complex objective functions. Previously, traditional methods of modelling involved OVAT (one variable

at a time), factorial Design of Experiments (DOE), and Response Surface Methodology (RSM) but many inadequacies exist. In some situations, ANN is superior to these conventional methods due to not requiring previous knowledge on specific chemical events governing the desired process, as well as being highly adaptive with parallel-processing for error and failure tolerance [45].

As the name suggests, artificial neural networks are believed to mimic the internal workings and learning process of brain neurons. ANN is a universal function approximator that has the ability to estimate any continuous function to an arbitrary precision without any prior knowledge on the structure of the function that is being approximated, such as reaction mechanisms or thermodynamics. They are able to analyze large data sets which comprise of non-linear connections where simple descriptive mathematical equations are not sufficient. Artificial neural networks as a predictive model provide several advantages when being applied to linear and non-linear systems such as [46];

- learns and is highly adaptive to recognizing patterns
- can continue even if a few elements fail due to parallel connections
- eliminates the requirement to develop an explicit model of a specific process

Learning models such as ANN constructs a network of central relationships between inputs and desired outputs, coupled to each other with connections called neurons encompassed within hidden layers. Each neuron amongst the ANN is attributed with a weight parameter and interconnections to the neurons from the previous layer (input or hidden), each connection with its own attributed weight. The number of neurons in the hidden layer of the ANN are an effective parameter in the learning performance of the model. If the number of neurons in the hidden layer is too small, then the network learning function is unable to converge to an optimal value (underfitting), demonstrating an oscillatory behaviour of the error function, and thus cannot acquire the relationship among the input–output designs. If the number of neurons is too high, then the input–output list is simply stored, and it shows a poor generalization performance known as overfitting [47]. Causal relations, not correlated, between inputs and outputs can then be determined from a trained ANN assembly by comparing determined outputs with desired outputs to obtain the best possible outcome. [23]. The typical structure of a neural network containing 1 input layer, 1 hidden layer, and 1 output layer and an overview of a single node is displayed in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Structure of a general feed forward network with 1 input layer, 1 hidden layer, and 1 output layer (left) and an overview of a node amongst the network (right). (x_i is training data, n^i is the total number of

connections, c^i are inputs, d^i are outputs, weight of each connection is represented by w^i , specific bias is b^i , and Ψ_i denotes the activation function at the i -th node).

Naturally, there are some disadvantages associated with the use of ANN. Due to the fact that these models are considered as a *black box* approach; it limits the ability to identify causal relationships between parameters. They are also highly restricted to their specified range of operating conditions for which they are trained for, and it is at times problematic to predict outside of this range of data. Therefore, the prediction quality of trained ANN is highly dependent on the quantity and quality of training data related to the process, and results can differ significantly if different sets of input data are employed for training purposes. To ensure efficient ANN development, data collected from experimental tests are randomly divided into training sets for determining connection weights between layers, and test sets for evaluation of model accuracy. Furthermore, large neural networks that are sometimes implemented quickly require increasingly high processing time and resources, comparable to the previous mechanistic examples, which is undesirable for most applications.

Additional types of artificial neural networks exist that couple supplementary algorithms and principles to improve predictive accuracy and interpretation. For example, adaptive neuro fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) combines ANN with fuzzy logic principles, most commonly based on Takagi-Sugeno Fuzzy rules. Detailed information on the principles of Takagi-Sugeno Fuzzy model approximator can be found elsewhere [48]. Although ANN are capable of self-learning, its knowledge is difficult to interpret whereas fuzzy inference is able to transform this into a more comprehensible form that forecasts the probability of an event to happen or not, but lacks any learning capability. Fuzzy Logic (FL) is a method that is said to resemble or imitate human reasoning and decision making where instead of the typical functions of TRUE or FALSE in Boolean logic, fuzzy logic considers intermediate levels of possibilities between the two (partial truths) [49]. An overview of a common Takagi-Sugeno ANFIS topology is presented in Figure 7.

Figure 7: Example of the structure of a Takagi-Sugeno adaptive neuro-fuzzy system (ANFIS) implemented for transesterification. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [50]. Copyright 2018 Elsevier Ltd.

Genetic algorithms (GA), based on Darwin's theory of evolution through natural selection, have also been applied to ANFIS networks to enhance their optimization capabilities via random changes generating new solutions. In GA, a population of solutions undergo a sequence of random mutation and crossover alterations directed towards a superior performing (ideal) range of values, and the model is biased towards the fittest solution, which is hopefully representative of the most optimal solution of that population [51]. The newly formed population of solutions is then implemented into the next series of iterations until a satisfactory level of fitness is attained. By implementing ANFIS systems with particle swarm optimization (PSO) algorithms, it is possible to improve approximation proficiencies and minimize estimation errors by tuning parameters. PSO, related to the natural movement of birds or insects, starts with a random selection of solutions that are steered around a searched mathematical space in terms of velocity and position. Based on the collective best known positions achieved, the "swarm" of solutions is steadily guided towards the solution of best fit. Unlike GA, PSO lacks crossover and mutations but requires less parameters and is easier to implement. Figure 8 shows the general synopsis of how GA and PSO-based algorithms undergo optimization procedures within fuzzy inference systems.

Figure 8: General schematic of GA-ANFIS (left) and PSO-ANFIS algorithms (right).

Artificial intelligence systems are progressively becoming widely accepted as a convenient technology that is able to deal with non-linear problems, and once successfully trained, can perform precise predictions and generalizations at high speeds. ANN has been implemented in the conventional sense of the petroleum refinery concept with fossil fuel conversion processes for unit operations, reactor design, and optimization purposes. A major advantage of relying on empirical values from fossil fuel processes over bio-based alternatives is the much more extensive database foundation that exists from the over 100 year history of the petroleum industry, enabling effective training when employed for neural networks. Table 2 displays a summary of the numerical findings and ANN methodology utilized in the following reviewed studies that have developed ANN for the utilization of fossil fuel conversion processes.

Table 2: Summary of Artificial Neural Networks Utilized in Fossil Fuel Conversion Processes.

Process	Feedstock	Inputs	Outputs	Type of ANN	ANN structure	Number of datasets for training/testing/validation	Agreement*	Reference
Bubble point pressure	Crude oil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reservoir temperature Solution gas-oil ratio Gas gravity Oil gravity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bubble point pressure 	BPFFANN	4-6-1	532/144/144	$R^2 = 0.977$ RMSE = 306 SD = 0.200	[52]
Fischer-Tropsch synthesis	Natural gas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reaction time Operating pressure Temperature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CH₄ CO₂ CO 	BPFFANN - GA	5-8-1 4-7-1 4-9-1	162/54/54	$R^2 = 0.99$ MSE < 0.005	[53]
	---	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature pressure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CO conversion CH₄ selectivity C₅ selectivity 	BPFFANN	2-(6 or 8)-1	15/3/3	$R^2 = 0.96 - 0.99$	[54]
	Natural gas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pressure Temperature Time Ratio of CO/H₂ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> CH₄ CO₂ CO 	BPFFANN	4-7-9-3	70 total	$R^2 = 0.91$ RMSE = 0.66, 1.94, and 1.41	[55]
Steam reforming	Glycerol	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reaction pressure Sweep factor 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Glycerol conversion Total hydrogen yield Hydrogen recovery H₂, CO, CO₂ Selectivity 	BPFFANN	2-10-6	70%/15%/15%	$R^2 = 0.9998$ MSE < 0.049	[56]
HDS	Naphtha	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Input flow rate Temperature Pressure H₂ / HC ratio H₂ Purity H₂ Consumption Sulfur content Inlet IBP Inlet FBP Specific gravity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Outflow flow rate Effluent sulfur content ΔT ΔP Product IBP Product FBP Specific gravity of product 	BPFFANN	7-5-4 3-3-3	100/60/37	$R^2 = 0.918$ and 0.890	[57]
	Gas oil fractions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mass fraction of petroleum cut Feed density Feed distillation curve Sulfur concentration of feed Catalyst time on stream 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Kinetic parameters Heat of reaction Maximum specific H₂ consumption 	BPFFANN	5 - (4 to 7) - 4	--	$R^2 = 0.39$ to 0.82	[58]
	Gas oil fractions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total flow rate Inlet temperature Pressure Hydrogen rich gas flow rate Light cycle oil flow rate Feed density 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sulfur in product 	BPFFANN	6-6-1	220/29/--	$R^2 = 0.95$ and 0.94 MAE = ~5	[59]

Methanol production	Syngas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Temperature · Syngas composition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · CO conversion · Methanol yield 	BPFFANN	5-4-2	--	--	[60]
Distillation unit	Crude oil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Crude composition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Cut points of Naptha, kerosene, diesel, and AGO 	ANN-GA	33-13-17-16-4	164/--/28	R ² = 0.99	[61]
	Crude oil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Feed specific gravity · Temperature · Several volumetric flowrates · Pressure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Several D86 95% · Temperatures 	BPFFANN	13-9-6	1041/446/446	R ² = 0.998 MSE = 183	[62]
Oxidative Dehydrogenation	Propane	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Catalyst composition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Propene yield 	BPFFANN	8-5-1	216/10/--	Relative error of 14%	[63]

* All correlation coefficients and errors are reported for the testing portion of the model unless stated otherwise

3.1 Fischer-Tropsch Synthesis

Fischer-Tropsch (FT) synthesis can produce liquid hydrocarbons as transportation fuels from synthesis gas through indirect liquefaction of solid (coal) or gaseous (natural gas) carbon-based sources. FT has been a pinnacle process in the petroleum industry for almost a century using fossil fuels, although the method can be easily transferred to biomass feedstocks with few deviations. Fischer-Tropsch reaction mechanism is still not completely understood, making artificial neural networking a suitable tool for such a process. Esfandyari et al. developed an ANN for the FT synthesis of natural gas over Co/alumina catalysts based on experimental tests conducted in a 1 L autoclave reactor for network training. Using reaction conditions such as pressure and temperature alongside initial gas composition, they were able to forecast final gas yields of CH₄, CO₂, and CO with decent agreement to experimental results with a R^2 of 0.91 [55]. Another study employed GA coupled with ANN modeling to predict molar fractions of methane, carbon dioxide, and carbon monoxide using operational reaction parameters of time, temperature, and pressure as inputs. Predicted gas compositions were in excellent agreement with experimental values when a genetic algorithm was utilized with much higher accuracy relative to the standard trial-and-error ANN models [53]. The authors concluded that operation time was the most influential parameter in predicting CH₄ molar percentage in the product gas. Others applied artificial neural networking to predict CO conversion and resulting product yields from Fischer-Tropsch synthesis over Fe-Ni/Al₂O₃ catalysts based on only reaction temperature and pressure [64]. Although a rather small set of experiments of only 13 were used for training of the ANN, the authors reported good agreement for estimated conversion and methane selectivity compared to experiment results.

3.2 Hydrodesulfurization and Hydrotreatment

An ANN model was developed for the prediction of sulfur content in the hydrotreated product resulting from a commercial HDS unit [59]. Six variables were continuously monitored online during hydrodesulfurization of gas oil fractions with a large set of 220 data was utilized to train the ANN model. Validation of the model with predicted values and laboratory qualitative analysis demonstrated very good agreement to accurately predict sulfur content for quality control and optimization purposes. Although, this was likely a result of the rather narrow fluctuations in sulfur content that occurred during training experiments as well as testing due to a rather constant feed of gas oil fractions. Arce-Medina et al. investigated the use of two different neural network structures for the application of hydrosulfurization to remove sulfur from naphtha [57]. Ten individual operational parameters obtained from an industrial-scale refinery were considered amongst three neural networks with differing structures (10-8-7, 7-5-4 and 3-3-3). A decent agreement was achieved for the neural networks with 7 and 3 inputs with an R^2 of 0.9 and 0.89 respectively, but the larger network encompassing all 10 inputs was deemed too complex and would require a larger number of datasets to be accurately trained. Bellos et al. used a hybrid neural network to predict catalyst deactivation rate due to desulfurization and hydrogenation reactions amongst three different hydrotreaters [58]. Based on feed quality and catalyst time on stream, they were able to evaluate kinetic parameters from industrial data to then predict the HDS reactor performance for three fixed-bed units. Kinetic parameter correlation factors were tolerable during training ranging from 0.72 to 0.95, although generally dropped during validation data obtained from experiments with R^2 between 0.39 – 0.82. This drop in correlation during validation of the ANN was likely a result of simplifying catalyst deactivation to too few feed parameters. With enhancements to predictability, these results could be essential for industrial HDS operations to determine the optimal time to extract used catalysts for regeneration or replacement.

3.3 Crude Oil Distillation and Bubble Point Pressure

A hybrid, multi-output artificial network combined with a genetic algorithm was applied to the operation of a crude distillation unit to optimize cut point temperatures and energy efficiency in a petroleum refinery with several different crude compositions [61]. A multi-output methodology using 33 compositional parameters were implemented to account for expected uncertainties in the crude oil feedstock. The predicted cut points together with diesel production values were identified to be a more feasible technique compared to the straight run Taguchi method in terms of accuracy and process time. Fadhil Ahmed and colleagues demonstrated the ability for ANN to act as process controllers for a crude oil distillation unit within the largest active oil refinery in Iraq, the Baiji Oil Refinery [62]. Two different types of neural network control systems (6 controllers each, 1 for each output) were trained with an extraordinary 1040 recorded data sets obtained from the crude distillation unit and validated with a remaining 446 sets, resulting in a near flawless correlation coefficient. The ANN controllers were successfully able to quickly handle step changes in temperatures with minimal overshooting to maximize distillation efficiencies of major products. Authors developed an ANN model for the prediction of bubble point pressure of crude oils as a function of solution gas-oil ratio, reservoir temperature, oil gravity (API), and gas specific gravity as inputs [52]. This parameter can be obtained through experimental techniques, although is often very expensive and time-consuming. An extensive range of 760 experimental data sets collected from several leading oil fields, varying in geographical location as well as crude feedstock, were used for training purposes to evaluate the performance of 56 different neural network structures. Based on obtaining the lowest values for average absolute percent relative error and root mean square error in addition to the highest correlation coefficient, a Levenberg-Marquardt neural network structure containing 6 neurons in the hidden layer was determined to be the most optimal. Solution gas-oil ratio was reported to be the input with the highest contribution in determining bubble point pressure and accuracy of the ANN model outperformed all existing empirical correlations reported elsewhere.

3.4 Steam Reforming, Methanol Production, and Dehydrogenation

ANN has also been applied for water-gas shift reactions, a major step in steam gasification to convert the excess water and CO into more desirable CO₂ and hydrogen. An ANN model was developed for estimation of hydrogen yield and recoverability during glycerol steam reforming in a Pd-Ag membrane reactor in the presence of Co/Al₂O₃ catalyst [56]. Agreement between predicted values and experimental results were excellent with a near perfect correlation coefficient despite relying on only two inputs. This was largely due to the experimental data used for testing hardly deviated from expected. Others have also investigated the use of ANN for a multi-step process of methanol production from syngas in a lab-scale packed bed reactor where authors used syngas composition with reaction temperature as inputs to predict outputs of final CO and methanol yields [60]. Agreement between modelled predictions and experimental data from validations tests were reported as satisfactory, although unfortunately no exact correlation coefficients were reported.

A first of its kind study was conducted by Holeňa and Baerns that utilized a neural network to predict propene yields during oxidative dehydrogenation of propane based on solely catalyst composition [63]. The neural model was trained with tests performed with over 200 catalyst compositions comprising varying amounts of B, Fe, Ga, La, Mg, Mn, Mo, and V at constant operational reaction conditions, then was

validated with 10 unsystematically chosen catalysts. Although the model was only applicative to a specific set of reaction conditions, the ANN scheme was able to predict with significant accuracy the yield of propene with a relative error of 14%, although a specific correlation coefficient was not reported. This example excellently demonstrates the plausible capability for artificial neural networks to accurately resolve a causal relationship between catalyst design and product yields without any prior knowledge on reaction mechanisms or transport phenomena that are imperative when applying mechanistic modelling approaches.

4. Machine Learning Implementation for Biorefinery Optimization

Major advancements have been made in the field of artificial intelligence with the development of Industry 4.0 to accelerate productivity and mass production technologies. The vision for the newly recognized Industry 5.0 underlines the need for synergy between human and machine which the previous Industry 4.0 ignores that will facilitate sustainability and waste prevention in the future bioeconomy. Mathematical modelling will be an essential tool for the innovation of novel biorefinery concepts to be able to efficiently handle ever-changing feedstock compositions while simultaneously maintaining optimal production rates of bio-based products and minimizing waste generation. The following examples are pioneer studies for the state-of-the-art application of artificial intelligence systems for the optimization of operating conditions and product yields for particular conversion processes involved in biorefinery approaches. Table 3, 4, and 5 present structure and methodology summaries of the studies later discussed that have implemented artificial neural networks for the purpose of biomass conversion routes using thermochemical, chemical, and biochemical processes, respectively.

Table 3: Summary of Artificial Neural Networks Implemented for Thermochemical Biomass Conversion Processes.

Process	Feedstock	Inputs	Outputs	Type of ANN	ANN structure	Number of datasets for training/testing/validation	Agreement	Reference
Combustion	Black liquor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Liquor flow · Feed water · Air flows 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Net steam · SO₂ · NO_x · O₂ 	BPFFANN	6-130-4	1512/--/168	MAPE = 1.77 – 14.72	[65]
	Municipal solid waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Waste inlet flow · Speed of grate · Primary air flow · Secondary air flow 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Steam · Oxygen 	BPFFANN	--	--	--	[66]
Gasification	Mixed sawdust and woodchips	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Biomass composition · Moisture content · Air input 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Syngas composition · Process temperature 	ANFIS	--	4/--/1	Prediction Error within ~10±%	[67] [68]
	Tannery Wastewater Sludge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Syngas concentration · Calorific value 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Change in Calorific value 	BPFFANN	7-12-1	3/3/--	R ² = 0.68 – 0.98	[69]
	Poplar sawdust, pine sawdust, bagasse, and cotton stem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Ash content · Moisture content · Elemental composition (C, O, H) · Gasification temperature · Equivalence ratio · Injected steam ratio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Product gas yield · Gas composition (CO, CO₂, H₂, CH₄) 	BPFFANN	8-2-1	43/11/--	R ² > 0.98	[49] [70]
	Woody biomass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · C, O, H content · Ash content · Moisture content · Reduction zone temperature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · CH₄ % · CO % · CO₂ % · H₂ % 	BPFFANN	6-(5 or 3)-1	44/19/19	R ² > 0.98	[71]
	biomass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · C, O, H, N, S elemental analysis composition · Moisture content · Ash content · Volatile matter · Fixed carbon · Gasifier temperature · Air to fuel ratio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Net output power 	BPFFANN	11-40-1	722/309/--	R ² > 0.999	[72]
	Mixed sawdust and woodchips	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Fuel flow rate · Air flow rate · Fuel injection Frequency · Syngas outlet T 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Syngas composition · Process temperature 	ANFIS	--	4/5/--	Prediction error of ~30% and ~7%	[73]
Pyrolysis	Pine sawdust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Space velocity · Reaction temperature · Particle size 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Gas product selectivity (CO, CO₂, H₂, CH₄) 	BPFFANN	3-7-4	85%/15%/--	R ² > 0.99	[74]
	<i>Tithonia diversifolia</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Temperature · Heating rate · Flow rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Bio-oil yield 	BPFFANN	4-14-1	21/9/9	R ² = 0.995	[75]

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Particle size 						
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Cotton cocoon shell · Tea waste · Olive husk · Hazelnut shell 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Temperature · Lignin · Cellulose · Hemicellulose · Fix carbon · Volatiles · Moisture · Ash 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Solid · Liquid · Gas 	BPFFANN	8-9-3	9/9/--	$R^2 = 0.99$ MSE = 5.17	[47]
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Cotton cocoon shell · Tea waste · Olive husk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Biomass Type · Catalyst Type · Catalyst amount · Temperature 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Percentage of Hydrogen-rich gas produced 	BPFFANN	4-13-1	102/33/33	$R^2 = 0.96$ MSE = 6.97	[76]
	Lignocellulosic biomass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Biomass composition (cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Activation energy (E_a) · Pre-exponential coefficient (k_0) · Order of reaction (n) 	BPFFANN	3-(17,20,30)-1	105/23/23	$R^2 = 0.93, 0.92, 0.95$	[77]
	Refuse derived fuel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Temperature · Heating rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Weight loss 	BPFFANN	2-7-6-1	700/150/150	$R^2 = 0.99995$	[78]
	Lignocellulosic biomass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Biomass composition (cellulose, hemicellulose, lignin) · Heating rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Activation energy (E_a) · Pre-exponential coefficient (k_0) · Order of reaction (n) 	ANFIS-PSO	Membership function = 49, 38, 55	154/38/--	$R^2 = 0.98, 0.96, 0.99$ RMSE = 2.18, 1.15, 0.09 MAPE = 1.58%, 4.04%, 1.93%	[79]
	Lignocellulosic biomass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Carbon · Oxygen · Hydrogen · Nitrogen · Sulfur · Process heating rate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Reaction order · Frequency factor · Activation energy 	ANFIS and GA-ANFIS	--	119/30/--	$R^2 = 0.845$ and 0.964	[80]
	Lignocellulosic biomass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Fixed carbon · Volatile matter · Ash content · C, O, H content · Carbonization temperature · Carbonization time · Activation temperature · Activation time · Steam to biochar ratio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Total yield · BET surface area 	BPFFANN	11-(1-19)-2	109/23/23 +13 for a second validation	$R^2 > 0.92$ MSE < 0.01	[81]
	Biodiesel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · FAME compositions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Cetane number 	BPFFANN	11-5-1	48/--/15	$R^2 = 0.95$	[82]

Thermal Properties	Biomass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Fixed Carbon · Volatile matter · Ash content 	· HHV	BPFFANN	3-3-1	88/43/43	$R^2 = 0.963$ RMSE = 0.375	[83]
	Biomass	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Fixed carbon · Volatile matter · Ash content 	· HHV	ANFIS, GA-ANFIS, and PO-ANFIS	--	247/106/--	$R^2 = 0.923, 0.969,$ and 0.976 RMSE = 0.656, 0.450, and 0.3287	[84]
	Biochar	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Fixed carbon · Volatile matter · Ash contents 	· HHV	BPFFANN	3-5-1	91/38/38	$R^2 = 0.9651$ MSE = 0.6502	[85]

* All correlation coefficients and errors are reported for the testing portion of the model unless stated otherwise

4.1 Thermochemical Processes

4.1.1 Gasification

Interest in gasification of biomass has thrived recently with new syngas production plants emerging but identifying accurate process parameters for optimal efficiency remains to be precisely determined. Several examples exist in the literature in which artificial neural network models have been developed that focus on gasification to help pinpoint optimal reaction conditions while using varying types of biomass feedstocks [86]. Since gasification encompasses several complex chemical reactions including thermal cracking, pyrolysis, and partial oxidation of combustible vapours and char, several assumptions must be made to simplify the process for modelling. ANN equipped with a back-propagation training algorithm was implemented to model gasification of wastewater sludge from a tannery facility [69]. The authors trained and tested the neural network with syngas composition (H_2 , O_2 , CH_4 , CO , CO_2 , and N_2) and calorific values (CV) as inputs obtained from experiments performed on a lab-scale, updraft fixed-bed reactor with varying air flow rates. Predictions for the change in CV over time were calculated as outputs and correlation coefficients ranged from 0.68 to 0.98 depending on the specific operational conditions implemented. The predicted change in calorific values obtained from the ANN were shown to be less accurate with experiments that had lower flowrates of dried air due to lower conversion to gaseous products. Similarly, Puig-Arnavat et al. presented two separate ANN models applied to biomass gasification in both circulating and bubbling fluidized bed gasifiers [70][49]. Input variables were quite extensive which included biomass moisture, ash content, elemental composition of the biomass, gasification temperature, equivalent ratio, and injected steam ratio. Five individual neural networks (one for each output variable; product gas yield and gas composition (CO , CO_2 , H_2 and CH_4)) were integrated into the model to predict specific feedstock compositions that yield the highest amount of gas yield. A final neural network was presented that estimated product gases with exceptional agreements between modelled predictions and experimental values with regression coefficients while avoiding the complexity of standard kinetic models. They concluded that the elemental composition of the biomass feedstock (C, H, O) was the most influential variable for predicting producer gas yield in both circulating and bubbling fluidized bed gasifier configurations. Baruah et al. also developed an ANN model specifically for downdraft gasifiers for biomass gasification [71]. Unlike all other ANN examples for gasification, they included reduction zone temperature as a crucial factor that can greatly influence the occurrence of specific gasification reactions such as water-gas shift reaction and methanation. This was proven to be true with their developed ANN which identified reduction temperature had a dominating impact on final gas composition, and demonstrated very good agreement with experimental values. Similarly, Safarian et al. also demonstrated an effective ANN integrated with thermodynamic equilibrium modelling of a downdraft biomass gasifier [72]. A near perfect coefficient correlation was achieved to estimate net output power, though their model was exceptionally computationally exhausting with 11 inputs, 40 hidden neurons, and implemented over 1000 datasets from the literature, resembling more like mechanistic modelling approaches and limiting its applicability.

4.1.2 Pyrolysis

Thermochemical conversion routes of biomass such as pyrolysis is specifically difficult to predict through modelling methods due to the high temperature and harsh reaction media typically containing a large amount of radicals and ions. Often complex phenomenological models are utilized to model pyrolysis

processes that collectively calculates heat and mass transfer differential equations, though this approach is frequently very computationally intensive. Several groups have attempted to provide appropriate neural network methodologies that can accurately elucidate such a complex yet vital process in the biorefinery approach. Sun and colleagues reported an artificial network for pyrolysis of pine sawdust that relied on space velocity, reaction temperature, and particle size as inputs to predict product gas composition [74]. Following training and testing of the neural network with experimental values obtained with an in-house pyrolysis reactor, they reported excellent agreement ($R^2 > 0.99$). Reaction temperature was identified as the main contributor for product gas composition. Another group presented an ANN method in attempts to predict the percentage of liquid (tar), solid (char), and gaseous products resulting from pyrolysis of four different types of biomass waste [47]. Feedstock composition percentage of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin of each biomass variation together with reaction temperature, moisture content, ash content, fixed carbon, and volatiles were utilized as inputs. The neural network was firstly trained with nine randomly selected experimental data sets, then an additional 9 experimental values were provided to validate the neural network. Modeled predictions indicated reasonable fitting with a R^2 and MSE coefficients of 0.99 and 5.17, respectively. Similarly to the previous example, authors established temperature to be the most impactful parameter when it came to predicting pyrolysis products. Even though a small selection of samples were used for training, the ANN demonstrated satisfactory predictability due to a very narrow range of input values in the validation data. The same authors then later reported a more extensive neural network to predict the ratio of hydrogen-rich gas (H-rG) produced following pyrolysis and sequential gas filtration in a lab-scale system [76]. Contrarily to their first study, rather than feedstock composition, inputs included feedstock type (cotton cocoon shell, tea waste, and olive husk), catalyst type (Na_2CO_3 , K_2CO_3 , and ZnCl_2) and amount, and reaction temperature. Compared to their previous study, this adaptation simplified the necessary number of input variables from 8 down to 4, streamlining their ANN and eliminating the need for conducting time-consuming proximate analysis of the various biomasses. A larger experimental set of 102 data were implemented for training of the ANN with an additional 33 experiments utilized for testing and validation purposes. This larger collection of training data provided substantial prediction capability ($R^2 = 0.955$) for the tested and validation sets despite the considerable deviation of hydrogen-rich gas production between experiments. A comparative study was conducted between RSM and ANN methodologies for estimating bio-oil yield during pyrolysis in a fixed-bed reactor setup [75]. The developed ANN model outperformed the RSM in predicting bio-oil yield during the validation segment when comparative experiments were performed. The authors were able to omit the use of inputs regarding feedstock composition from their neural network architecture since they only focused on a specific type of biomass, *Tithonia diversifolia*. Therefore, this allowed the presented ANN to accurately estimate overall bio-oil yield with a simple model framework and a small set of datasets for training which contained little deviations. Sunphorka et al. developed three individual ANN models to predict kinetic parameters (activation energy (E_a), pre-exponential factor (k_0), and reaction order (n)) based only on the composition of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin as inputs based on thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) experimental data [77]. A diverse range of biomass types in addition to pure cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin samples were analyzed to provide 150 experimental data sets randomly divided for training and testing purposes. They reported decent agreement of kinetic parameters between predicted and experimental values with R^2 of 0.93, 0.92, and 0.95 for E_a , k_0 , and n , respectively. They concluded cellulose composition had a strong effect on the pre-exponential factor, whilst hemicellulose had a stronger effect on the reaction order. Following testing, they investigated how the predicted kinetic parameters obtained by the ANN model correlated with values attained experimentally via pyrolysis of rice straw. The agreement was acceptable with $R^2 = 0.94$, however, there were substantial inconsistencies at very low and high temperatures. This was described to be due to the improper assumption that only single-step decomposition occurred during thermal degradation of the biomass samples rather than several degradation steps which is more commonly

recognized to take place. Another study took a different direction by estimating the yield and surface area of activated carbon formed following biomass pyrolysis and then carbon activation using a very in-depth ANN scheme [81]. Although an experimentally intensive list of up to 11 parameters were utilized as inputs which would be undesirable in practice, the model was able to predict with relatively good agreement. Three different ANN scenarios were tested which either relied on compositional data from ultimate analysis, proximate analysis, or a combination of both. They concluded that no difference was observed between approaches but feedstock composition was once again the most influential factor. Another unique study successfully utilized ANN to estimate the thermal behavior of refuse-derived fuel produced from municipal wastes [78]. The developed ANN framework resembled more closely to those described for fossil fuel conversion where an enormous list of empirical data was used for training and a very simple ANN structure with no inputs related to feedstock composition was covered. Nonetheless, they optimized their ANN by examining 300 possible topology configurations and a near perfect correlation was achieved when compared to experimental validation tests.

Aghbashlo et al., pioneers in the field of ANFIS for the application of biomass conversion, employed an adaptive network-based fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) augmented with particle swarm optimization (PSO) to estimate the kinetic parameters for pyrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass [79]. Applying conventional modelling methods is extremely difficult for such an application due to the intrinsic heterogeneity and non-uniform nature of lignocellulosic biomass, in addition to the complexity and non-linearity of the pyrolysis process. The ANFIS-PSO model was trained and tested with TGA values collected from a broad pool of data previously reported in the literature, mostly by Sunphorka et al. [77] in which they aimed to improve on their more traditional ANN. The established ANFIS network provided an excellent fit of the pyrolysis kinetic constants with $R^2 = 0.98, 0.96, \text{ and } 0.99$ for $E_a, k_0, \text{ and } n$, respectively, exceeding those obtained by Sunphorka et al. Secondly, they then validated the predictive capability of the model on calculating pyrolysis kinetic constants on three new biomass feedstocks not previously tested (*Spartina alterniflora*, *Miscanthus*, and cherry stone) and they achieved substantial agreements with $R^2 = 0.99, 0.92, \text{ and } 0.97$, respectively. This study exemplifies the prevailing learning and estimation efficiency that can be achieved in accurately foreseeing an exceptionally non-linear system such as biomass pyrolysis when employing an ANFIS fuzzy system in combination with a PSO algorithm to rapidly search and identify global optimums. More recently, ANFIS with and without GA optimization has also been applied to estimate kinetic parameters of different biomasses based on ultimate analysis data and heating rate [80]. In exchange for a considerably longer computational time of 282 seconds, up from 6 seconds, improved accuracy in predicting kinetic parameters was achieved when applying the hybrid ANFIS-GA system which was more competent in finding global optimums than the gradient-based classical ANFIS model. This trade in accuracy in place of an extended computational time must be considered when constructing and comparing these more complex, hybrid systems. Depending on the application of the neural network, a slight improvement in accuracy may not be desirable if the computational time is excessively prolonged. Another fuzzy logic based neural network was proposed by Lerkkasemsan using reaction time alongside composition of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin in biomass to better understand the influence that the uncertainties in biomass composition have on pyrolytic reactions [87]. By implementing 81 distinct fuzzy if-then rules, the ANFIS model resulted in 92% and 97% prediction accuracy when tested against pyrolysis experiments performed on two non-specific biomass species, *P. pinnata* and *J. curcas*.

4.1.3 Thermal Properties

Neural networks have also been utilized to estimate thermal properties of biomass as they are vital parameters for thermochemical conversion processes and unit operations which are often difficult or expensive to obtain through experimental methods. HHV of biomass is an important characteristic to be determined accurately, quickly, and cheaply for effective design and operation of process systems. HHV of biomass cannot be simply determined by formation enthalpies of CO₂ or H₂O because of its complexity as a feedstock and the inability to determine accurate bond energies. Furthermore, HHV and proximate analysis parameters are not a linear relationship. The higher heating value (HHV) of potential bio-based fuels can be assessed experimentally by bomb calorimeter to determine combustion enthalpies, however, this is not always practical to perform and mathematical equations to relate values are inconsistent in the literature as they are heavily dependent on the type of biomass used. Several groups have begun exploring the capability of artificial neural networks to precisely predict the HHV of various biomasses, typically based on the large amount of literature data from proximate (fixed carbon, volatile matter, and ash content) or thermogravimetric analysis. Obafemi et al. has recently presented an explicit review on the latest neural network studies on estimating HHV of biomass, thus we included only a few selected examples here which encompass a variety of neural network schemes and/or were published after the fact [25]. Uzun et al. applied an artificial neural network based on an extensive list of proximate analysis data (fixed carbon, volatile carbon, and ash content) of 131 biomass variations from the literature [83]. The study investigated and evaluated 78 different topologies of neural network configurations, of which a simple 3-3-1 topography resulted in the highest correlation coefficient and lowest RMSE. Furthermore, its predictability outperformed most other models presented in the literature to accurately estimate HHV for a range of biomasses. Others have implemented an adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) with the same proximate datasets in addition to extra data from related literature [84]. Optimization of parameters were accomplished with both particle swarm optimization (PSO) and genetic algorithm (GA), and their predictability was compared with a basic ANFIS model. After training of all three neural systems with 247 data points, the performance of both the PSO and GA hybrid models were found to be superior compared to the plain ANFIS model. Furthermore, the PSO-based ANFIS model resulted in the highest correlation coefficient of 0.98, slightly higher than with GA optimization. This would imply that PSO may be a more efficient optimization algorithm compared to GA to estimate the HHV of biomass as a result of distinct particles learning from local optimums to effectively identify the best global solution rather than relying on crossovers. Very recently, HHV of biochar was investigated using an ANN model based on only simple proximate analysis obtained from literature [85]. Although the authors only explored a small range of hidden neurons from 3-10, their developed model was reported to have excellent fit when validated with experimental data and could offer an alternative to HHV values obtained via bomb calorimetry.

Table 4: Summary of Artificial Neural Networks Implemented for Chemical Biomass Conversion Processes.

Process	Feedstock	Inputs	Outputs	Type of ANN	ANN structure	Number of datasets for training/testing/validation	Agreement	Reference
Transesterification	Castor oil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · MeOH : oil molar ratio · Catalyst loading · Temperature · time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · FAME yield 	ANFIS	--	130/26/--	$R^2 = 0.987$ RMSE = 2.2391	[88]
	Palm kernel oil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · MeOH : oil molar ratio · Catalyst loading · Reaction time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Acid value 	ANN-GA and ANFIS-GA	3-10-1	12/3/3	$R^2 > 0.99$	[89]
	Waste cooking oil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Reaction temperature · Ultrasonic irradiation time · MeOH : oil molar ratio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Conversion efficiency · Specific energy consumption 	ANFIS	3 inputs 1 output 27 fuzzy rules	17/5/5	$R^2 = 0.99$ RMSE ≈ 0.00 MAPE ≈ 0.00	[90]
	Waste cooking oil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Reaction temperature · Residence time · MeOH : oil molar ratio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Cost per unit of exergy · Environmental impact per unit of exergy 	ANFIS	---	27 total	$R^2 > 0.99$	[91]
	Sesame oil	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Catalyst concentration · Reaction time · MeOH : oil molar ratio 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · FAME content 	BPFFANN	4-10-1	18/6/6	$R^2 > 0.96$	[92]
Hydrolysis	Rice straw	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Biomass loading · Particle size · Time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Glucose and xylose concentrations 	BPFFANN	3-8-2	84/18/18	$R^2 = 0.97$ MSE = 15.55	[93]
	Apple pomace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Enzyme loading · Substrate loading · Initial pH · Temperatures · Combinations of each 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Glucose and reducing sugars concentrations 	BPFFANN	20-20-6-1	54/13/13	$R^2 = 0.99$	[94]

* All correlation coefficients and errors are reported for the testing portion of the model unless stated otherwise

4.2 Chemical Processes

4.2.1 Transesterification

Transesterification has also been subjected to neural network approximations for the relative simple formation of biodiesels at mild reaction temperatures from vegetable oils. A novel approach was applied for biodiesel production from sesame oil using ultrasonication that was able to predict fatty acid methyl ester (FAME) content with relative success [92]. A design of experiments (DoE) approach was conducted to perform a concise set of 27 experiments varying catalyst concentration, reaction time, methanol:oil ratio, and temperature later used as inputs. The generalization capability of the training set was exceptionally high with a correlation coefficient of 0.997, however, fell considerably short in the validation stage with an R^2 of only 0.78. This precision is unsatisfactory in most situations and a much larger and more diverse set of experiments utilized for training of the neural network is necessary to enhance the models predictability. Yue et al. attempted to improve the prognostic capability of implementing fuzzy logic through ANFIS modelling approaches to estimate FAME yields. They demonstrated that a fuzzy interference system was effective at achieving a good fit with a small relative deviation between predicted and experimental data [88]. A comparison was also conducted by Betiku et al. between ANN and ANFIS models coupled with GA for transesterification of palm oil using the same inputs as the previous example [89]. Prior to inclusion of GA optimization, ANN and ANFIS performed equivalently when predicting the acid value of palm oil during esterification experiments with $R^2 > 0.99$ even though an even smaller set of only 17 experiments were included in both training and testing of the models. When GA optimization was incorporated into each of the two neural networks to determine optimal reaction conditions to obtain a minimum acid value, ANN surpassed the ANFIS model when validated with experimental values. Although both models were programmed to undergo 50 generations, both models reached the minimum acid value after only 8 generations and remained constant, implying that no crossovers or ‘mutations’ between parameters were plausible that could impact the acid value of the palm oil. Others have similarly applied multi-objective ANFIS modeling networks to predict and optimize biodiesel production from waste cooking oil via transesterification in an elaborate, piezo-ultrasonic reactor [90]. Two separate ANFIS models were implemented that were trained with reaction temperature, ultrasonication time, and alcohol/oil molar ratio as inputs from 27 experiments to estimate separately the optimal conversion efficiency and specific energy consumption. Approximations for both conversion efficiency and specific energy consumption using 27 fuzzy rules were determined to be virtually flawless with R^2 values of 0.99 and nearly 0.00 for both MSE and MAPE. Following testing of the independent ANFIS models, a third fuzzy network was performed to determine the optimal operational conditions to achieve ASTM standards of biodiesel with the minimum specific energy consumption, but unfortunately no transesterification test was performed to validate this prediction. The ANFIS scheme that relied on fuzzy algorithms with locally-modified objectives was found to be marginally better compared to the others without. The authors point out that this is a result of this algorithm architecture taking into account supports and conflicts more locally rather than globally which transpires with interdependent or independent fuzzy systems. The same authors developed an additional ANFIS network with the same empirical data to instead predict cost and environmental impact per unit of exergy [91]. By optimizing transesterification conditions to meet ASTM standards, they were able to minimize cost and energy requirements instead of exclusively focusing on maximizing yields which most other studies emphasize. In terms of the bioeconomy and sustainable energy production, this application of ANN could be invaluable to minimize waste production and pollution generation. Biodiesel can be difficult to predict accurate cetane number since there are numerous chain lengths formed during transesterification. Using 48 different fatty acid methyl ester compositions, Piloto-Rodriguez et al. implemented a neural

network model to estimate the cetane number of biodiesel fuels with good agreement [82]. Interestingly, nearly all studies report few experimental data points (<32) while almost exclusively achieving exceptional correlation coefficients of >0.99, although not a single study has considered water as an input in their ANN and used only pure oil feedstocks. This would not be the case when implemented into a large-scale biorefinery using more raw biomass resources that contains a large quantity of water which has been shown to be detrimental to conversion and FAME yield [95]. Biodiesel production via transesterification may be one specific biorefinery process where ANN/ANFIS modelling could be a valuable predictive tool as minimal feedstock composition parameters are required as inputs where lower reaction temperatures are needed, however, the influence of the high water content associated with biomass must be considered in future networks.

4.2.2 Hydrolysis

Vani et al. developed a neural network to estimate the sugar yield of rice straw following enzymatic hydrolysis by utilizing biomass loading, substrate particle size, and reaction (incubation) time as inputs [93]. Based on 84 experiments for training, 18 for validation, and 18 for testing, the model presented excellent regression R^2 value of 0.97 and 0.96 for glucose and xylose, respectively. They concluded that sugar yields were heavily dependent on biomass loading, whereas particle size was insignificant. Their developed ANN model was able to optimize hydrolysis conditions to maximize sugar yields. Similarly, a neural network was established by Gama et al. that was applied to predict enzymatic hydrolysis of apple pomace. Unlike the previous example, the authors relied on a completely different set of parameters as inputs which were temperature, pH, enzyme and substrate loadings to determine optimal release of glucose and reducing sugars [94]. Once again, they were able to predict the best conditions to maximize glucose and reducing sugar yields, although the training and testing data set contained minimal fluctuations. Enzymatic hydrolysis may also be a specific process that would benefit significantly from ANN technologies which like transesterification, does not require specific feedstock composition details as input and occurs at quite mild and more stable conditions compared to most thermochemical processes.

Table 5: Summary of Artificial Neural Networks Implemented for Biochemical Conversion Processes.

Process	Feedstock	Inputs	Outputs	Type of ANN	ANN structure	Number of datasets for training/testing/validation	Agreement	Reference
Fermentation	Glucose	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature Initial pH Glucose concentration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Substrate degradation efficiency Hydrogen yield Avg. hydrogen production rate 	BPFFANN	3-5-1	29/--/3	$R^2 = 0.98, 0.99, 0.98$	[96]
	Sugar Cane Molasses	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> pH Temperature Inoculum volume Molasses Concentration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hydrogen production 	BPFFANN - GA	4-(6-10)-1	23/--/6	$R^2 = 0.85-0.91$	[97]
	Sugars	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Media concentrations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Scleroglucan concentration 	BPFFANN- GA	4-3-1	30/17/--	$R^2 = 0.98$ Avg. error = 6.5 % RMSE = 0.73	[98]
	Waste water	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Volumetric inflow rate of wastewater Recirculated sludge Raw sludge flow Concentrated sludge flow Supernatant clear water Sludge flow to filter press and thickener Concentration of phosphorus Chemical Oxygen Demand Biological Oxygen Demand Concentration of nitrogen Total suspended solid 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Biogas yield 	BPFFANN CGFFANN	12-13-9-1	105/52/52	$R^2 = 0.97$ Error = 0.12	[99]
	Swine and cow slurry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Day of measurement Dry matter Dry organic matter pH Conductivity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Methane production 	BPFFANN	5-(7 or 11)-1	285/145/140	$R^2 > 0.98$	[100]
	Sugar beet	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fermentation time Starting sugar content Substrate type 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Bioethanol content Yeast cell number Sugar content 	BPFFANN	3-12-1	--	$R^2 = 0.999$ MSE > 0.005	[101]
	Peanut hull	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Temperature pH Retention time Total solids Volatile solids 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Total Biogas yield 	BPFFANN	--	50/1/--	$R^2 = 0.9972$ RMSE = 42.12	[102]

	yeast	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Glycerol · NH₄Cl · MgSO₄ · KH₂PO₄ 	· Lipid yield	ANN-GA	--	21/9/9	R ² = 0.9918	[103]
	Saw dust, cow dung, banana stem, rice bran and paper waste	· Concentration of biomass	· Total biogas yield	BPFANN - GA	5-2-1	20/--/5	--	[51]
Anaerobic Digestion	Municipal solid waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · pH · Moisture content · Methane % · Total volatile solids · Volatile fatty acids · Biogas production 	· Methane %	BPFANN	5-4-1	4 total (multi-day operations)	R ² = 0.54	[104]
	Landfill	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · pH · alkalinity · Chemical oxygen demand · Sulfate · Conductivity · Chloride · Waste Temperature · Refuse Age 	· Methane fraction in landfill gas	BPFANN	8-(15 or 12)-1	34 months of continuous operation 50%/25%/25%	R ² = 0.51 – 0.96	[105]
	Wastewater	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · pH · alkalinity · Total volatile acids 	· Influent feed flow rate	ANFIS	3-(20, 25, or 30) - 1	250 datasets total	R ² = 0.92	[106]
	Food waste leachate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · LFG extraction rate · LFL : FWL ratio 	· Methane fraction	BPFANN	2-15-1	92/39/--	R ² = 0.71 – 0.88	[107]
	Cattle manure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Working days · Influent chemical oxygen demand · Influent pH · Influent alkalinity · Influent ammonia · Influent total phosphorous · Hydraulic retention time · Waste adding ratio · Pretreatment · Reactor number 	· Biogas production rate	BPFANN	10-4-1	90/45/45	R ² = 0.75	[108]
	Wastewater	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Reactor fill ratio · Influent pH · Effluent pH · Influent alkalinity · Effluent alkalinity · Organic loading rate 	· Biogas production rate	BPFANN	10-22-1	36/12/12	R ² = 0.9852	[109]

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Effluent chemical oxygen demand · Effluent total suspended solids · Effluent suspended solids · Effluent volatile suspended solids 						
	Animal and plant commercial waste	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Temperature · Total solids · Volatile solids · pH 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Methane fraction 	BPFANN-GA	4-25-25-1	177/--/50	$R^2 = 0.87$	[110]
	Sludge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Organic loading rates · pH · Volatile fatty, propionic, and acetic acid concentration · Gas production and composition 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · pH · Volatile fatty, propionic, and acetic acid concentration · Gas production and composition 	BPFANN	3-3-1 9-3-3 9-3-2	500/--/350	$R^2 > 0.8$	[111]

* All correlation coefficients and errors are reported for the testing portion of the model unless stated otherwise

4.3 Biochemical Processes

4.3.1 Fermentation

Models for fermentation processes are problematic to develop and validate due to the non-linear nature of biochemical interactions and the large number of possible metabolic reactions that can take place with the use of enzymes and/or microorganisms. Therefore, artificial neural networks have been recently considered as a possible alternative to help address this non-linearity that other modelling techniques such as RSM which are unsuitable for fitting complex systems. ANN provides 2 main advantage relative to RSM: (i) ANN does not require prior specification of suitable fitting function and (ii) ANN has universal approximation capability, i.e. it can approximate most non-linear functions including quadratic functions, whereas RSM is limited to fitting with polynomial approximations [98]. A comparative study was made between implementing an ANN coupled with GA optimization and response surface modelling (RSM) to identify operating conditions for reaching maximum hydrogen production during bio-hydrogen fermentation of cane molasses [97]. Both models demonstrated good fitness during training, although validation results when using predicted optimal reaction conditions indicated that the neural network accounted for much greater variability with 15% error relative to excessive overestimation of 119% error for the RSM model. Similarly, another comparison study was conducted to evaluate RSM and ANN-GA modelling approaches to optimize the fermentation media towards the production of scleroglucan, a fungi produced glucan [98]. Inputs consisted of four media components including sucrose, yeast extract, K_2HPO_4 , and $MgSO_4$ concentrations with scleroglucan concentration as output. Once again, ANN accuracy outperformed RSM methods for validation tests to obtain maximum scleroglucan yields with 2% prediction error compared to 8% for the latter. Another study predicted biogas yields generated from the anaerobic digestion of peanut hull and compared with both RSM and ANN modeling approaches. Both models considered temperature, pH, retention time, total solids, and volatile solids as inputs in attempt to estimate the total yield of biogas. Results obtained from experimental validation tests indicated very good agreement with predicted values with correlation coefficients for the ANN and RSM models of 0.99 and 0.89, respectively. The RSM model overestimated the produced yield of biogas which was explained as a result of poor variable interactions relative to the more robust ANN network, once again demonstrating the superior predictive performance of ANN [102]. These results clearly constitute the constraints that often emerge when attempting to model such complex, non-linear biochemical processes as fermentation using only polynomial approximations, justifying the exploration of applying ANN modelling techniques for more accurate estimations.

Authors developed a neural network model combined with GA to optimize biogas production from mini-pilot digester fermentations by only using the initial concentration of 5 different types of biomasses and/or wastes as inputs [51]. The ANN-GA model was trained and tested with 25 pilot experiments which lead to a modest 8% increase in biogas production after relying on the model to estimate optimal substrate concentrations without using any information of water content, pH, or actual substrate composition. Wang et al. applied a neural network to predict and optimize reaction conditions for fermentation to produce (bio)hydrogen gas from digested seed sludge [96]. Process optimization by one-factor-at-a-time experimental design has been widely performed, but such designs do not consider all the interactive effects among different factors. Therefore, they constructed the ANN to consider temperature, initial pH, and glucose concentration as inputs to predict resulting substrate degradation efficiency, hydrogen yield, and average hydrogen production rate following fermentation. Even with a relatively small subset of experiments used for training of only 29, the authors reported good agreements with $R^2 > 0.98$. A validation

experiment was also performed to compare the predicted operating parameters to obtain maximum substrate degradation efficiency with outstanding agreement. Another study applied an artificial neural network for bioethanol production through fermentation of sugar beets to predict final ethanol content, yeast cell number, and residual sugar content based on only fermentation time, starting sugar content, and substrate type as inputs [101]. The authors did a thorough investigation of identifying the most optimal neural network architecture and ensuring precise connection weights by examining 15 different ANN arrangements with 20 replicates each. The final developed model revealed good agreement with experimental validation results and demonstrated artificial neural networks to be a valuable tool for fermentation of sugars to bioethanol. The optimization of microbial lipid formation from yeast was also investigated by ANN-GA for the purpose of biodiesel production [103]. The hybrid GA model was successfully able to optimize the fermentation media nutrients to maximize lipid content 250% higher than initially tested which was validated with experiments.

4.3.2 Anaerobic Digestion

Nair et al. reported an ANN to assess methane yields from the formation of biogas during anaerobic digestion of municipal solid waste in a lab-scale bioreactor [104]. Using inputs of pH, biogas production, moisture content, and volatile solids, the network demonstrated decent correlation coefficients for training and validation from 4 separate 20-day experiments, however, the proposed network fell extremely short during the testing segment with a $R^2 = 0.54$. The variability when utilizing an unreliable feedstock such as municipal waste without considering compositional differences in the ANN framework, in combination with the uncertainty that accompanies biological systems, lead to a weak generalization capability. Methane production from bovine and porcine slurry fermentation was estimated by artificial neural network using slurry dry matter content, pH, and conductivity parameters [100]. Implementing over 900 empirical datasets for training, validation, and testing across two different neural network formats resulted in superb agreement to accurately predict cumulated methane production. Exact feedstock composition of the manure was not needed, though slurry dry matter and organic matter were identified to be key factors in methane emissions. Others have also used neural networks to estimate the methane generation of biogas from the landfill of a food waste recycling plant in South Korea by applying only landfill gas extraction rate and landfill: food waste ratio of leachate as inputs [107]. Initially, the ANN struggled to align with observed methane content when relying on only 60% of the datasets for training from the 130 days of field testing, however, was significantly enhanced when trained with 80% of the data by improving R^2 from 0.79 to 0.88. GA coupled with ANN has also been investigated for the optimization of methane production from a digester of a biogas plant [110]. Similar to the previous example, an extended duration of operational plant data for 177 days was obtained for the study. After validation of the neural network with a decent correlation coefficient of 0.87, methane yield during simulation was improved by nearly 7% by tuning operational conditions, however, no actual experiment was performed to confirm this prediction. The methane fraction from field-scale landfill bioreactors was also estimated using a neural network based on an extensive list of 8 leachate and bioreactor parameters as inputs which was collected over almost 3 years of continuous operation [105]. Although this is one of the earliest anaerobic digestion studies utilizing ANN compared to the previous examples, the developed model was able to predict methane production with excellent agreement. The authors were able to overcome the inconsistencies of municipal solid waste by measuring a broad range of parameters including waste temperature, sulfates, and chloride concentrations which others did not take into consideration. Tufaner et al. reported two studies to estimate biogas production from cattle manure co-digest with various municipal wastes, and wastewater [108] [109]. Their first study struggled

with trying to cope with the variation of wastes used for co-digestion, resulting a subpar R^2 of 0.75 in the validation portion. This unsatisfactory predictability of their model was likely a result of offsetting due to the low number of only 4 neurons in the hidden layer that the authors decided upon, thus causing underfitting and failing to achieve the most optimal conditions. On the other hand, several years later the same authors presented an analogous study to estimate biogas production from anaerobic digestion of synthetic wastewater. Interestingly, their developed ANN had the same number of inputs and 36 training datasets (only 40% as many datasets as their first study), yet they achieved a much higher R^2 of 0.985. Contrarily, their newly developed ANN model contained 22 neurons in the hidden layer which probably addressed the underfitting problem that was inferred to occur in their first study, allowing a much higher generalization capability. It's interesting to point out that when investigating the optimum number of hidden neurons, if the authors only searched in the range of 1-10, such as the case in their initial study, they would have most likely ended up with a similar underfitting issue as 8 hidden layer numbers had a comparable MSE as 22.

5. Modelling for Simulations, Intensification & Control

Process intensification through dynamic control can be particularly beneficial for the efficiency of biorefineries and their overall economic feasibility. Intensifications that minimize purification steps, maintains high yields and production rates, and consumes less reagents and energy can greatly reduce lignocellulosic processing costs. A key problem to perform dynamic, on-line monitoring of a process or reactor is that each function evaluation may require from minutes to hours of calculation time, and when using evolutionary algorithms, hundreds of evaluations are sometimes needed [112]. Thus, artificial neural networks are a possible method to simplify such models for faster monitoring and response times to maintain desirable operating conditions for optimal energy consumption and resulting yields.

Compared to coal, gasification of biomass generally is more reactive and unstable due to the increased oxygen and water content which requires a faster combustion response, making effective process control more difficult [113]. Several studies have implemented intricate simulations for the gasification of wood wastes in both downdraft and updraft gasifiers using elaborate kinetic rate and thermodynamic equilibrium models [114][115]. The simulations are able to accurately identify the influence of reaction temperature and air supply on syngas composition and yields for better reactor design and unit operations, however, these modelling approaches are too complex for quick parameter prediction and are impractical for online process control. Therefore, artificial neural networks are a possible alternative that could quickly analyze the effects of various operating parameters in reasonable time and computational costs. Mikulandrić et al. presented an ANFIS network for the on-line control of an active 75 kW gasification demonstration facility in Germany [68]. The model was able to predict with moderate precision ($\pm 10\%$) the composition of product syngas along with syngas temperature while monitoring on-line process parameters such as temperature, air and fuel flows for up to 12 hours of operation. The same authors then utilized ANFIS to predict on-line process parameters such as syngas composition and reaction temperature by collecting data from two different types of gasifiers (Combi-gasifier and co-current fixed bed gasifier) currently operating in Germany [67]. To verify the generalization capability of the neural network, they performed model prediction tests and obtained decent correlation for syngas temperature around $\pm 10\%$ relative to experimental values. Similarly, they also report a dynamic neural network model (ANFIS) for the gasification of biomass trained with only 9 experiments performed in an 75 kW co-current fixed bed gasifier

industrial plant [73]. Outputs of syngas composition (H_2 , CO, and CH_4) and process temperature were predicted by using fuel flow rate, air flow rate, fuel injection frequency, and syngas outlet temperature as inputs over 70 hours of plant operation. Due to the quantity of available data sets being relatively limited at the time of publication, the neural network had a relatively large prediction error of 7.06% for process temperature and 26.4%, 29.9%, and 38.3% for H_2 , CO, and CH_4 , respectively. Despite this rather large prediction error, the developed model was capable of on-line, dynamic re-training sessions that only took 10 seconds to analysis incoming data and estimate future operating parameters. This feature would allow superior generalization capability once submitted to longer operation data for training.

Due to the increased water and oxygen content of biomass relative to fossil fuel feedstocks, its combustion for heat generation can be slow and challenging to effectively control. Pirouti et al. developed a dynamic model for the controlling of the unit operations for the direct-combustion of biomass [113]. During simulation the model was effectively able to regulate operating parameters such as air fuel ratio, steam flow, and supply temperature to control pressure and maintain optimal power output during combustion of several different types of biomass. Operational instabilities such as slugging and fouling as a result from unexpected deviations in feedstock were also lessened by the simulated control system compared to prior installment of the simulator. Gölles and colleagues have published several works that present simplified models that are able to predict and control a grate firing unit in a biomass combustion plant requiring only a few operational parameters [116][117][118]. A unique approach was implemented where all individual units of the biomass boiler including fuel bed, heat exchanger, combustion zones, and air fuel supply were modelled separately off-line, then discrete models were merged together and validated experimentally. CO emissions and actuator limitations were mitigated with the implementation of the control system on both small- and medium-scale commercial biomass boiler systems. An artificial neural network was also offered to dynamically control the air emissions from a biomass boiler used in the Kraft process of an industrial pulp mill in Finland [65]. A range of process variables were collected over the course of three months of operation for training and validation of several different neural network structures. An ideal ANN type with 130 hidden neurons was selected that was able to estimate key air emission outputs of SO_2 , NO_x , O_2 , and net steam during 1 week of simulation, demonstrating the potential of an ANN to control air emission release during real operation. The model however struggled with predicting SO_2 and NO_x emissions when compared to actual results and was reported to be possibly due to the seasonal differences in biomass where nitrogen content is considerably higher in the roots during winter months. Furthermore, such an exceptionally large number of neurons in the hidden layer not only requires high computational costs, but also can lead to overfitting problems. Leskens et al. also reported the application of a neural network control system for a municipal solid waste combustion plant for performance improvement [66]. The model was able to dynamically monitor reaction conditions including waste inlet and air flows to control steam and oxygen flows to account for fluctuations in waste composition and uphold a desirable performance level.

Fermentation is a particular process that requires effective modelling tactics for precise monitoring and parameter control in real-time whereas not to harm the productivity of the active microorganisms [43]. This can be quite laborious for such biological systems as many key parameters can be challenging to continuously monitor, not to mention the lack of understanding of the alterations in metabolic rates. Nonetheless, Americano and colleagues established an effective control system for an actual industrial-scale, ethanol fermentation unit [119]. By fitting the fermentation facility with a regulatory control system that was able to dynamically tune fermentation operating conditions including pH, temperature, and reactor level, they were able to enhance total ethanol production by almost 7% compared to when the control

system was not implemented. An overview of their developed process control system for a fermentation unit is displayed in Figure 9. An extraordinary study was carried out to predict and monitor the fermentation of *S. cerevisiae* by utilizing only on-line 2D fluorescence measurements and requiring zero offline measurements [120]. Authors overcame the disadvantage of time-consuming and often expensive data-driven models by instead using a theoretical-based process model to train and calibrate their ANN with simulated parameters of biomass, glucose, and ethanol concentrations obtained from 120 fluorescence intensity spectra obtained exclusively online. Since neural network training is nondeterministic and weights are randomly selected initially, their approach simultaneously investigated 1000 different neural networks at each step. They then subsequently selected the median rendition to account for outliers. Although this method was rather computationally demanding which needed around 90 minutes to perform each step, their network had comparable generalization capabilities compared to an alternative ANN model that relied on offline measurements to estimate specific growth rates.

Figure 9: Schematic representation of a process control system for a fermentation unit.

Recently, a state-of-the-art neural network was presented for the process intensification of a current, industrial-scale, wastewater treatment plant which utilizes wastewater sludge for anaerobic fermentation to produce biogas [99]. The model simultaneously monitored seven adjustable plant operation parameters including sludge flows and volumetric flowrates, together with five water quality parameters such as P and N concentrations, for the purpose to maximize resulting biogas yields. Astonishingly, more than 1000 data sets were recorded over an entire 3 year continuous plant operational time period, of which 210 were integrated into the neural network system. The ANN was moderately able to predict, adjust, and dynamically control process parameters to direct flow streams for the enhancement of biogas production with a decent R^2 of 0.74. Considering that the wastewater treatment plant had inflows of wastewater over 25,000 m^3 per day and had to handle such an erratic feedstock such as wastewater sludge, this study is one of the best demonstrations in the literature thus far for the application of ANN as a valuable tool towards process intensification purposes on an industrial scale.

Waewsak et al. presented an excellent demonstration of an ANN being utilized for the regulation of a laboratory-scale anaerobic hybrid reactor of wastewater using a neural-fuzzy control system [106]. Process

parameters including pH, alkalinity, and total volatile acids were predicted each day while the fuzzy logic was applied to calculate the daily influent feed flow rate of the reactor to maintain optimal feeding of the bacteria for maximum methane production. Even under induced overloaded shock conditions, the neural-fuzzy logic control system demonstrated excellent process response rates to maintain a stable environment and high methane yields. Holubar et al. implemented a similar ANN to control methane production during anaerobic digestion of wastewater sludge [111]. By employing a hierarchical scheme of three different neural networks to monitor such parameters as pH, organic loading rate, and volatile fatty acid content in an anaerobic CSTR, the objective function was reached and methane production was maintained above 60% for greater than 17 days of continuous operation. This is another example where the ANN demonstrated a conservative correlation coefficient of only 0.8, but was adequate enough for rapid dynamic regulation and control of a complicated process where faster response rates were preferred.

6. Conclusions and Outlook

Computational learning algorithms are rapidly growing in reputation as powerful predictive tools and have been recognized as having enormous potential in a range of diverse disciplines, and bio-based chemical production is no exception. Most of the main biomass conversion routes relevant for biorefineries have been investigated with the use of ANN in the attempt to gain more insight into these complex reaction systems. These networks provide several benefits compared to traditional modeling methods since they do not require a prior reaction mechanism or thermodynamic knowledge to be adequately programmed. Many studies have demonstrated, on both lab-scale and industrial level, the potential for ANN as a “black-box” program that attempts to account for fluctuating feedstocks and a regularly unstable reaction environment that are typical for biorefinery processes.

When applying ANN models for biomass conversion processes, there exists several shortcomings that are not as prevalent when being applied towards petroleum conversion processes. Contrary to biorefineries, processes regarding the conversion of fossil fuels do not have to deal with the challenges associated with inconsistent feedstock compositions and moisture levels. This is clearly illustrated in the poor performance that is generally associated with studies that try to prognosticate the conversion of municipal waste or wastewaters which significantly varies between sources or even the same source. As demonstrated in the literature, this allows ANN models applied for petroleum-based operations to be much more tolerant to a narrower range of training data with fewer outliers that must be considered. In terms of biomass conversion, ANN often require a much more robust training dataset to account for feedstock deviations which can greatly influence operating conditions and product yields. Additionally, ANN applied for fossil fuel conversion do not require as many (or any) inputs to account for feedstock composition compared to with biomass. This provides two opportunities; i) either allows the development of more simple and straightforward ANN methodologies with fewer overall inputs, or ii) allows the ability to include more relevant parameters regarding operating conditions as inputs to enhance generalization capability. This also subsequently demands more time-consuming and costly elemental measurements. Several groups attempt to circumvent this by concentrating on just one specific type of biomass, or even species, which leads to a much better estimation potential. However, these models would be severely limited to undesirable Phase I biorefineries, greatly restricting its economic potential. Furthermore, unlike newly conceptualized biorefineries, there exists a much more extensive collection of empirical data available in the petroleum industry that can be exploited for effective training of neural networks. An insufficient collection of empirical data can sometimes lead to overfitting and makes it difficult for the ANN to converge to an

optimal value. Available empirical data is continuously expanding everyday related to biomass conversion processes but will still require considerable developments to better handle the intense variability.

In terms of ANN topology, there still lacks a standardized method in choosing the most suitable number of neurons in the hidden layer and largely depends on intuition of the operator. Since neural network training is nondeterministic in nature, most examples rely on a trial and error approach to explore a range of hidden neurons to ultimately decide the most optimal number that minimizes the root mean square error or correlation coefficient. This method obviously at first glance appears to achieve excellent predictability during training, but often falls short during testing and validation stages with issues of underfitting. This was demonstrated perfectly by the sequential studies presented from Tufaner et al. when attempting to estimate biogas yield during anaerobic digestion of wastes [108][109]. The authors were able to significantly improve their network predictability by expanding their search of suitable number of hidden neurons to a wider range of possibilities, from 8 up to 22, which was not originally investigated in their first study. This should become common practice for all future work to examine a much broader selection of hidden neurons rather than stopping at the first one that gives the lowest error. Fuzzy interference systems such as hybrid ANFIS models, which instead group up and evaluate inputs based on if-then rules, have also been shown to be more adaptive and capable of enhancing the generalization capability of traditional ANN models for more complex, non-linear systems. Both types of frameworks can be combined with GA and PSO optimization algorithms which facilitate finding more appropriate local optimums rather than global. However, this exchange of accuracy for computational time must be carefully considered depending on the application as either a predictive function to estimate key parameters, or as a dynamic control system to monitor and regulate a process based on quick, on-line measurements. The latter perhaps does not require perfect correlation to be effective and rather rapid, computational estimations would be a priority.

From the examples described in this review, the specific biomass conversion processes that could benefit the most from ANN technologies are likely those that are performed under lower and milder conditions (i.e. chemical and biochemical) such as transesterification, hydrolysis, and fermentation. ANN models seem to more frequently struggle when being applied for thermochemical routes that require harsh operating conditions and elevated temperatures which are more unpredictable and susceptible to fluctuations in water content and feedstock composition. As a result of this, thermochemical processes seem to require an ANN structure with a greater number of inputs in the attempt to account for these variations, increasing not only computational power but also requiring more time-consuming feedstock analysis such as proximate and elemental analysis. This also limits its applicability to be implemented for monitoring and dynamic control which should depend on less empirical data and simpler network methodology for faster parameter monitoring and response rates. Therefore, most applications in the literature that successfully employed neural networks as dynamic control systems were either rudimentary combustion, or biochemical processes, specifically fermentation and anaerobic digestion. Additionally, few examples exist in the literature that apply ANN approximations to chemical processes, which are largely confined to transesterification. Although most of the cases obtain an excellent fit when validated against experimental results, all the studies exclusively focused on pure oil sources and none of the studies considered water content in their ANN framework. Water would be an imperative factor to consider when using more relevant untreated biomass as a feedstock for transesterification rather than pure vegetable oils.

It is clear from the presented examples that the implementation of ANN towards biorefineries is still certainly in its infancy where literature remains relatively limited focusing on mainly simple systems that do not depend on too many connections or neurons. Since the predictability of these models are highly dependent on empirical data for effective training, the development of more powerful computational strategies and larger databases for specific biorefinery conversion processes are needed to enhance their

applicative capability. Improvements in the response times resulting from intelligent control structures will also be necessary for effective real-time, dynamic monitoring and control of reactions and unit operations. Nonetheless, mathematical modeling will be a crucial tool for the advancement of novel biorefinery concepts.

Acknowledgments

The authors would like to appreciatively acknowledge the financial support of by the EU Framework Program for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020 under Grant agreement no. 814416 (Reaxpro) and the Slovenian Research Agency (Program P2-0152 and the projects J2-2492, J2-1723).

References

- [1] G. Sorrosal, C. Martin, C.E. Borges, A.M. Macarulla, A. Alonso-Vicario, An optimisation strategy for the catalytic transformation of bioethanol into olefins using computational intelligence, *CEUR Workshop Proc.* 1422 (2015) 115–120.
- [2] R. Katiyar, S. Banerjee, A. Arora, Recent advances in the integrated biorefinery concept for the valorization of algal biomass through sustainable routes, *Biofuels, Bioprod. Biorefining.* 15 (2021) 879–898. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.2187>.
- [3] G. Jungmeier, M. Hingsamer, R. van Ree, Biofuel-driven Biorefineries A Selection of the Most Promising Biorefinery Concepts to Produce Huge Volumes of Road Transportation Biofuels until 2025, *IEA Bioenergy. Task 42* (February 2013) 38. https://www.nachhaltigwirtschaften.at/resources/iea_pdf/iea_task_42_biofuel_driven_biorefineries_lr.pdf
- [4] A. Amore, P.N. Ciesielski, C.Y. Lin, D. Salvachúa, V.S.I. Nogué, Development of Lignocellulosic Biorefinery Technologies: Recent Advances and Current Challenges, *Aust. J. Chem.* 69 (2016) 1201–1218. <https://doi.org/10.1071/CH16022>.
- [5] B.K. Das, P. Kalita, M. Chakraborty, *Integrated Biorefinery for Food, Feed, and Platform Chemicals*, Elsevier Inc., Chapter 21, 2016, pp. 393–416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-802980-0.00021-3>.
- [6] F. Cherubini, G. Jungmeier, M. Wellisch, T. Willke, I. Skiadas, R. Van Ree, E. de Jong, Toward a common classification approach for biorefinery systems, *Biofuels, Bioprod. Biorefining.* 3 (2009) 534–546. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.172>.
- [7] E. de Jong, G. Jungmeier, *Biorefinery Concepts in Comparison to Petrochemical Refineries*, Elsevier B.V., Chapter 1, 2015, pp. 3–33 <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63453-5.00001-X>.
- [8] V. De Buck, M. Polanska, J. Van Impe, Modeling Biowaste Biorefineries: A Review, *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.* 4 (2020) 1–19 <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2020.00011>.
- [9] R. Vinoth Kumar, K. Pakshirajan, G. Pugazhenthii, *Petroleum Versus Biorefinery-Based Platform Chemicals*, Elsevier Inc., Chapter 3, 2016, pp. 33–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-802980-0.00003-1>.

- [10] P. Choudhary, P.P. Assemany, F. Naaz, A. Bhattacharya, J. de S. Castro, E. de A. do C. Couto, M.L. Calijuri, K.K. Pant, A. Malik, A review of biochemical and thermochemical energy conversion routes of wastewater grown algal biomass, *Sci. Total Environ.* 726 (2020) 137961. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.137961>.
- [11] P. Ibarra-Gonzalez, B.G. Rong, A review of the current state of biofuels production from lignocellulosic biomass using thermochemical conversion routes, *Chinese J. Chem. Eng.* 27 (2019) 1523–1535. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjche.2018.09.018>.
- [12] L. Fülöp, J. Ecker, An overview of biomass conversion: Exploring new opportunities, *PeerJ.* 8 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj.9586>.
- [13] S.Y. Lee, R. Sankaran, K.W. Chew, C.H. Tan, R. Krishnamoorthy, D.-T. Chu, P.-L. Show, Waste to bioenergy: a review on the recent conversion technologies, *BMC Energy.* 1 (2019) 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s42500-019-0004-7>.
- [14] R. Karpagam, K. Jawaharraj, R. Gnanam, Review on integrated biofuel production from microalgal biomass through the outset of transesterification route: a cascade approach for sustainable bioenergy, *Sci. Total Environ.* 766 (2021) 144236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144236>.
- [15] A. Corma Canos, S. Iborra, A. Veltý, Chemical routes for the transformation of biomass into chemicals, *Chem. Rev.* 107 (2007) 2411–2502. <https://doi.org/10.1021/cr050989d>.
- [16] F. Cherubini, The biorefinery concept: Using biomass instead of oil for producing energy and chemicals, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 51 (2010) 1412–1421. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2010.01.015>.
- [17] S.S. Hassan, G.A. Williams, A.K. Jaiswal, Lignocellulosic Biorefineries in Europe: Current State and Prospects, *Trends Biotechnol.* 37 (2019) 231–234. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibtech.2018.07.002>.
- [18] K. Kohli, R. Prajapati, B.K. Sharma, Bio-based chemicals from renewable biomass for integrated biorefineries, *Energies.* 12 (2019) 233. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12020233>.
- [19] S.K. Maity, Opportunities, recent trends and challenges of integrated biorefinery: Part II, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 43 (2015) 1446–1466. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2014.08.075>.
- [20] I.H. V. Gue, A.T. Ubando, M.L. Tseng, R.R. Tan, Artificial neural networks for sustainable development: a critical review, *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy.* 22 (2020) 1449–1465. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-020-01883-2>.
- [21] M.I. Jahirul, R.J. Brown, W. Senadeera, I.M. O’Hara, Z.D. Ristovski, The use of artificial neural networks for identifying sustainable biodiesel feedstocks, *Energies.* 6 (2013) 3764–3806. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en6083764>.
- [22] A.O.B. Filho, I.M.A. Viegas, Applications of Artificial Neural Networks in Biofuels, *Adv. Appl. Artif. Neural Networks.* 10 (2018) 181–200. <https://doi.org/10.5772/intechopen.70691>.
- [23] Y. Sewsynker-Sukai, F. Faloye, E.B.G. Kana, Artificial neural networks: an efficient tool for modelling and optimization of biofuel production (a mini review), *Biotechnol. Biotechnol. Equip.* 31 (2017) 221–235. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13102818.2016.1269616>.
- [24] C. Xia, L. Cai, H. Zhang, L. Zuo, S.Q. Shi, S.S. Lam, A review on the modeling and validation of biomass pyrolysis with a focus on product yield and composition, *Biofuel Res. J.* 8 (2021) 1296–1315. <https://doi.org/10.18331/BRJ2021.8.1.2>.

- [25] O. Obafemi, A. Stephen, O. Ajayi, M. Nkosinathi, A survey of artificial neural network-based prediction models for thermal properties of biomass, *Procedia Manuf.* 33 (2019) 184–191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.promfg.2019.04.103>.
- [26] J.O. Ighalo, A.G. Adeniyi, G. Marques, Application of artificial neural networks in predicting biomass higher heating value: an early appraisal, *Energy Sources, Part A Recover. Util. Environ. Eff.* 00 (2020) 1–8. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15567036.2020.1809567>.
- [27] M.O. Daramola, A.O. Ayeni, Valorization of Biomass to Value-Added Commodities Current Trends, Challenges, and Future Prospects, *Green Energy and Technology*. Springer, Cham., 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-38032-8>
- [28] K.A. Demir, G. Döven, B. Sezen, Industry 5.0 and Human-Robot Co-working, *Procedia Comput. Sci.* 158 (2019) 688–695. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2019.09.104>.
- [29] I. Gosling, Process simulation and modeling for industrial bioprocessing: Tools and techniques, *Ind. Biotechnol.* 1 (2005) 106–109. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ind.2005.1.106>.
- [30] K. V. Gernaey, A.E. Lantz, P. Tufvesson, J.M. Woodley, G. Sin, Application of mechanistic models to fermentation and biocatalysis for next-generation processes, *Trends Biotechnol.* 28 (2010) 346–354. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibtech.2010.03.006>.
- [31] R. Vinu, L.J. Broadbelt, A mechanistic model of fast pyrolysis of glucose-based carbohydrates to predict bio-oil composition, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 5 (2012) 9808–9826. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c2ee22784c>.
- [32] X. Zhou, M.W. Nolte, H.B. Mayes, B.H. Shanks, L.J. Broadbelt, Experimental and mechanistic modeling of fast pyrolysis of neat glucose-based carbohydrates. 1. Experiments and development of a detailed mechanistic model, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 53 (2014) 13274–13289. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie502259w>.
- [33] X. Zhou, M.W. Nolte, B.H. Shanks, L.J. Broadbelt, Experimental and mechanistic modeling of fast pyrolysis of neat glucose-based carbohydrates. 2. Validation and evaluation of the mechanistic model, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 53 (2014) 13290–13301. <https://doi.org/10.1021/ie502260q>.
- [34] X. Zhou, W. Li, R. Mabon, L.J. Broadbelt, A mechanistic model of fast pyrolysis of hemicellulose, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 11 (2018) 1240–1260. <https://doi.org/10.1039/c7ee03208k>.
- [35] S. Hameed, A. Sharma, V. Pareek, H. Wu, Y. Yu, A review on biomass pyrolysis models: Kinetic, network and mechanistic models, *Biomass and Bioenergy.* 123 (2019) 104–122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2019.02.008>.
- [36] A. Boriouchkine, S.L. Jämsä-Jounela, Simplification of a mechanistic model of biomass combustion for on-line computations, *Energies.* 9 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.3390/en9090735>.
- [37] A.J. Griggs, J.J. Stickel, J.J. Lischeske, A mechanistic model for enzymatic saccharification of cellulose using continuous distribution kinetics I: Depolymerization by EG I and CBH I, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 109 (2012) 665–675. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bit.23355>.
- [38] S.E. Levine, J.M. Fox, H.W. Blanch, D.S. Clark, A mechanistic model of the enzymatic hydrolysis of cellulose, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 107 (2010) 37–51. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bit.22789>.
- [39] T. Jeoh, M.J. Cardona, N. Karuna, A.R. Mudinoor, J. Nill, Mechanistic kinetic models of enzymatic cellulose hydrolysis—A review, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 114 (2017) 1369–1385. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bit.26277>.

- [40] M. Huron, D. Hudebine, N. Lopes Ferreira, D. Lachenal, Mechanistic modeling of enzymatic hydrolysis of cellulose integrating substrate morphology and cocktail composition, *Biotechnol. Bioeng.* 113 (2016) 1011–1023. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bit.25873>.
- [41] H. Niu, N. Shah, C. Kontoravdi, Modelling of amorphous cellulose depolymerisation by cellulases, parametric studies and optimisation, *Biochem. Eng. J.* 105 (2016) 455–472. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2015.10.017>.
- [42] P. Bansal, M. Hall, M.J. Realff, J.H. Lee, A.S. Bommarius, Modeling cellulase kinetics on lignocellulosic substrates, *Biotechnol. Adv.* 27 (2009) 833–848. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biotechadv.2009.06.005>.
- [43] L. Mears, S.M. Stocks, M.O. Albaek, G. Sin, K. V. Gernaey, Mechanistic Fermentation Models for Process Design, Monitoring, and Control, *Trends Biotechnol.* 35 (2017) 914–924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tibtech.2017.07.002>.
- [44] L. Yu, P.C. Wensel, Mathematical Modeling in Anaerobic Digestion (AD), *J. Bioremediation Biodegrad.* S4 (2013) 003. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2155-6199.s4-003>.
- [45] M.A. Zamee, D. Won, Novel Mode Adaptive Artificial Neural Network for Dynamic Learning: Application in Renewable Energy Sources Power Generation Prediction, *Energies.* 13 (2020) 6405. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en13236405>.
- [46] A.M. Zador, A critique of pure learning and what artificial neural networks can learn from animal brains, *Nat. Commun.* 10 (2019) 3770. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-019-11786-6>.
- [47] B. Aydinli, A. Caglar, S. Pekol, A. Karaci, The prediction of potential energy and matter production from biomass pyrolysis with artificial neural network, *Energy Explor. Exploit.* 35 (2017) 698–712. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0144598717716282>.
- [48] B. Zhang, Y.C. Shin, A data-driven approach of Takagi-Sugeno fuzzy control of unknown nonlinear systems, *Appl. Sci.* 11 (2021) 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11010062>.
- [49] M. Puig-Arnavat, J.C. Bruno, Artificial Neural Networks for Thermochemical Conversion of Biomass, *Recent Adv. Thermochem. Convers. Biomass.* Chapter 5 (2015) 133–156. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-444-63289-0.00005-3>.
- [50] M. Aghbashlo, S. Hosseinpour, M. Tabatabaei, M. Mojarab Soufiyan, Multi-objective exergetic and technical optimization of a piezoelectric ultrasonic reactor applied to synthesize biodiesel from waste cooking oil (WCO) using soft computing techniques, *Fuel.* 235 (2019) 100–112. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2018.07.095>.
- [51] E.B. Gueguim Kana, J.K. Oloke, A. Lateef, M.O. Adesiyun, Modeling and optimization of biogas production on saw dust and other co-substrates using Artificial Neural network and Genetic Algorithm, *Renew. Energy.* 46 (2012) 276–281. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2012.03.027>.
- [52] A. Hashemi Fath, A. Pouranfard, P. Foroughzadeh, Development of an artificial neural network model for prediction of bubble point pressure of crude oils, *Petroleum.* 4 (2018) 281–291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.petlm.2018.03.009>.
- [53] H. Adib, R. Haghbakhsh, M. Saidi, M.A. Takassi, F. Sharifi, M. Koolivand, M.R. Rahimpour, S. Keshtkari, Modeling and optimization of Fischer-Tropsch synthesis in the presence of Co (III)/Al₂O₃ catalyst using artificial neural networks and genetic algorithm, *J. Nat. Gas Sci. Eng.* 10 (2013) 14–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jngse.2012.09.001>.
- [54] J. Tayebi, H. Atashi, F.F. Tabrizi, J. Gholizadeh, The hydrocarbon selectivity model for the

- Fischer- Tropsch synthesis on CO-Ni-ZrO₂ catalyst using Artificial Neural Network, 3 (2016) 475–484.
- [55] M. Esfandyari, M. Amiri, M. Koolivand-Salooki, Neural network prediction of the fischer-tropsch synthesis of natural gas with co (iii)/al₂o₃ catalyst, *Chem. Eng. Res. Bull.* 17 (2015) 25–33. <https://doi.org/10.3329/ceerb.v17i1.22915>.
- [56] K. Ghasemzadeh, F. Ahmadnejad, A. Aghaeinejad-Meybodi, A. Basile, Hydrogen production by a Pd–Ag membrane reactor during glycerol steam reforming: ANN modeling study, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy.* 43 (2018) 7722–7730. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2017.09.120>.
- [57] E. Arce-Medina, J.I. Paz-Paredes, Artificial neural network modeling techniques applied to the hydrodesulfurization process, *Math. Comput. Model.* 49 (2009) 207–214. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mcm.2008.05.010>.
- [58] G.D. Bellos, L.E. Kallinikos, C.E. Gounaris, N.G. Papayannakos, Modelling of the performance of industrial HDS reactors using a hybrid neural network approach, *Chem. Eng. Process. Process Intensif.* 44 (2005) 505–515. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cep.2004.06.008>.
- [59] I. Lukec, K. Sertić-Bionda, D. Lukec, Prediction of sulphur content in the industrial hydrotreatment process, *Fuel Process. Technol.* 89 (2008) 292–300. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuproc.2007.11.032>.
- [60] J. Ye, Artificial neural network modeling of methanol production from syngas, *Pet. Sci. Technol.* 37 (2019) 629–632. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10916466.2018.1560321>.
- [61] M.A. Durrani, I. Ahmad, M. Kano, S. Hasebe, An artificial intelligence method for energy efficient operation of crude distillation units under uncertain feed composition, *Energies.* 11 (2018) 2993. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11112993>.
- [62] D. Fadhil Ahmed, A.H. Khalaf, Artificial Neural Networks Controller for Crude Oil Distillation Column of Baiji Refinery, *J. Chem. Eng. Process Technol.* 07 (2015) 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.4172/2157-7048.1000272>.
- [63] M. Holeňa, M. Baerns, Feedforward neural networks in catalysis: A tool for the approximation of the dependency of yield on catalyst composition, and for knowledge extraction, *Catal. Today.* 81 (2003) 485–494. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0920-5861\(03\)00147-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0920-5861(03)00147-0).
- [64] H. Atashi, M. Hajisafari, F. Rezaeian, M.J. Parnian, Modeling of liquid hydrocarbon products from syngas, *Int. J. Coal Sci. Technol.* 6 (2019) 27–36. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40789-018-0232-3>.
- [65] P. Ruiz, G. Sorrosal, C.E. Borges, A.M. Macarulla, Modelling a biomass boiler using an artificial neural network, 28th Eur. Model. Simul. Symp. EMSS 2016. (2016) 296–302.
- [66] M. Leskens, L.B.M. Van Kessel, O.H. Bosgra, Model predictive control as a tool for improving the process operation of MSW combustion plants, *Waste Manag.* 25 (2005) 788–798. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2005.03.005>.
- [67] R. Mikulandrić, D. Lončar, D. Böhning, R. Böhme, M. Beckmann, Artificial neural network modelling approach for a biomass gasification process in fixed bed gasifiers, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 87 (2014) 1210–1223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2014.03.036>.
- [68] R. Mikulandrić, D. Lončar, D. Böhning, R. Böhme, Biomass gasification process modelling approaches, 0707 (2013) 1–13.

- [69] A. Ongen, H. Kurtulus Ozcan, S. Arayici, An evaluation of tannery industry wastewater treatment sludge gasification by artificial neural network modeling, *J. Hazard. Mater.* 263 (2013) 361–366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2013.03.043>.
- [70] M. Puig-Arnavat, J.A. Hernández, J.C. Bruno, A. Coronas, Artificial neural network models for biomass gasification in fluidized bed gasifiers, *Biomass and Bioenergy*. 49 (2013) 279–289. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2012.12.012>.
- [71] D. Baruah, D.C. Baruah, M.K. Hazarika, Artificial neural network based modeling of biomass gasification in fixed bed downdraft gasifiers, *Biomass and Bioenergy*. 98 (2017) 264–271. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2017.01.029>.
- [72] S. Safarian, S.M. Ebrahimi Saryazdi, R. Unnthorsson, C. Richter, Artificial neural network integrated with thermodynamic equilibrium modeling of downdraft biomass gasification-power production plant, *Energy*. 213 (2020) 118800. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.118800>.
- [73] R. Mikulandrić, D. Böhning, R. Böhme, L. Helsen, M. Beckmann, D. Lončar, Dynamic modelling of biomass gasification in a co-current fixed bed gasifier, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 125 (2016) 264–276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2016.04.067>.
- [74] Y. Sun, L. Liu, Q. Wang, X. Yang, X. Tu, Pyrolysis products from industrial waste biomass based on a neural network model, *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis*. 120 (2016) 94–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2016.04.013>.
- [75] N. Bhuyan, R. Narzari, S.M. Bujar Baruah, R. Katakai, Comparative assessment of artificial neural network and response surface methodology for evaluation of the predictive capability on bio-oil yield of *Tithonia diversifolia* pyrolysis, *Biomass Convers. Biorefinery*. (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-020-00806-x>.
- [76] A. Karaci, A. Caglar, B. Aydinli, S. Pekol, The pyrolysis process verification of hydrogen rich gas (H-rG) production by artificial neural network (ANN), *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*. 41 (2016) 4570–4578. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2016.01.094>.
- [77] S. Sunphorka, B. Chalermainsuwan, P. Piumsomboon, Artificial neural network model for the prediction of kinetic parameters of biomass pyrolysis from its constituents, *Fuel*. 193 (2017) 142–158. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2016.12.046>.
- [78] Ö. Çepeliogullar, İ. Mutlu, S. Yaman, H. Haykiri-Acma, A study to predict pyrolytic behaviors of refuse-derived fuel (RDF): Artificial neural network application, *J. Anal. Appl. Pyrolysis*. 122 (2016) 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaap.2016.10.013>.
- [79] M. Aghbashlo, M. Tabatabaei, M.H. Nadian, V. Davoodnia, S. Soltanian, Prognostication of lignocellulosic biomass pyrolysis behavior using ANFIS model tuned by PSO algorithm, *Fuel*. 253 (2019) 189–198. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.fuel.2019.04.169>.
- [80] M. Aghbashlo, F. Almasi, A. Jafari, M.H. Nadian, S. Soltanian, S.S. Lam, M. Tabatabaei, Describing biomass pyrolysis kinetics using a generic hybrid intelligent model: A critical stage in sustainable waste-oriented biorefineries, *Renew. Energy*. 170 (2021) 81–91. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2021.01.111>.
- [81] M. Liao, S.S. Kelley, Y. Yao, Artificial neural network based modeling for the prediction of yield and surface area of activated carbon from biomass, *Biofuels, Bioprod. Biorefining*. 13 (2019) 1015–1027. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bbb.1991>.
- [82] R. Piloto-Rodríguez, Y. Sánchez-Borroto, M. Lapuerta, L. Goyos-Pérez, S. Verhelst, Prediction of the cetane number of biodiesel using artificial neural networks and multiple linear regression,

- Energy Convers. Manag. 65 (2013) 255–261. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2012.07.023>.
- [83] H. Uzun, Z. Yıldız, J.L. Goldfarb, S. Ceylan, Improved prediction of higher heating value of biomass using an artificial neural network model based on proximate analysis, *Bioresour. Technol.* 234 (2017) 122–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2017.03.015>.
- [84] Z. Ceylan, E. Pekel, S. Ceylan, S. Bulkan, Biomass higher heating value prediction analysis by ANFIS, PSO-ANFIS and GA-ANFIS, *Glob. Nest J.* 20 (2018) 589–597. <https://doi.org/10.30955/gnj.002772>.
- [85] G. Çakman, S. Ghenni, S. Ceylan, Prediction of higher heating value of biochars using proximate analysis by artificial neural network, *Biomass Convers. Biorefinery.* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13399-021-01358-4>.
- [86] M. Puig-Arnavat, J.C. Bruno, A. Coronas, Review and analysis of biomass gasification models, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 14 (2010) 2841–2851. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2010.07.030>.
- [87] N. Lerkkasemsan, Fuzzy logic-based predictive model for biomass pyrolysis, *Appl. Energy.* 185 (2017) 1019–1030. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.02.105>.
- [88] X. Yue, Y. Chen, G. Chang, Accurate modeling of biodiesel production from castor oil using ANFIS, *Energy Sources, Part A Recover. Util. Environ. Eff.* 40 (2018) 432–438. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15567036.2017.1422058>.
- [89] E. Betiku, V.O. Odude, N.B. Ishola, A. Bamimore, A.S. Osunleke, A.A. Okeleye, Predictive capability evaluation of RSM, ANFIS and ANN: A case of reduction of high free fatty acid of palm kernel oil via esterification process, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 124 (2016) 219–230. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2016.07.030>.
- [90] M. Aghbashlo, S. Hosseinpour, M. Tabatabaei, A. Dadak, Fuzzy modeling and optimization of the synthesis of biodiesel from waste cooking oil (WCO) by a low power, high frequency piezo-ultrasonic reactor, *Energy.* 132 (2017) 65–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2017.05.041>.
- [91] M. Aghbashlo, M. Tabatabaei, S. Hosseinpour, On the exergoeconomic and exergoenvironmental evaluation and optimization of biodiesel synthesis from waste cooking oil (WCO) using a low power, high frequency ultrasonic reactor, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 164 (2018) 385–398. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2018.02.086>.
- [92] A. Sarve, S.S. Sonawane, M.N. Varma, Ultrasound assisted biodiesel production from sesame (*Sesamum indicum* L.) oil using barium hydroxide as a heterogeneous catalyst: Comparative assessment of prediction abilities between response surface methodology (RSM) and artificial neural network (ANN), *Ultrason. Sonochem.* 26 (2015) 218–228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ultsonch.2015.01.013>.
- [93] S. Vani, R.K. Sukumaran, S. Savithri, Prediction of sugar yields during hydrolysis of lignocellulosic biomass using artificial neural network modeling, *Bioresour. Technol.* 188 (2015) 128–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2015.01.083>.
- [94] R. Gama, J.S. Van Dyk, M.H. Burton, B.I. Pletschke, Using an artificial neural network to predict the optimal conditions for enzymatic hydrolysis of apple pomace, *3 Biotech.* 7 (2017) 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13205-017-0754-1>.
- [95] A. Karim, M. Amirul Islam, Z. Bin Khalid, C.K.M. Faizal, M.M.R. Khan, A. Yousuf, Microalgal cell disruption and lipid extraction techniques for potential biofuel production, Elsevier Inc., Chapter 9, 2019, pp. 129–147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-817536-1.00009-6>.

- [96] J. Wang, W. Wan, Application of desirability function based on neural network for optimizing biohydrogen production process, *Int. J. Hydrogen Energy*. 34 (2009) 1253–1259. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijhydene.2008.11.055>.
- [97] J.K. Whiteman, E.B. Gueguim Kana, Comparative Assessment of the Artificial Neural Network and Response Surface Modelling Efficiencies for Biohydrogen Production on Sugar Cane Molasses, *Bioenergy Res.* 7 (2014) 295–305. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12155-013-9375-7>.
- [98] K.M. Desai, S.A. Survase, P.S. Saudagar, S.S. Lele, R.S. Singhal, Comparison of artificial neural network (ANN) and response surface methodology (RSM) in fermentation media optimization: Case study of fermentative production of scleroglucan, *Biochem. Eng. J.* 41 (2008) 266–273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bej.2008.05.009>.
- [99] P. Sakiewicz, K. Piotrowski, J. Ober, J. Karwot, Innovative artificial neural network approach for integrated biogas – wastewater treatment system modelling: Effect of plant operating parameters on process intensification, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 124 (2020) 109784. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2020.109784>.
- [100] J. Dach, K. Koszela, P. Boniecki, M. Zaborowicz, A. Lewicki, W. Czekala, J. Skwarcz, W. Qiao, H. Piekarska-Boniecka, I. Białobrzewski, The use of neural modelling to estimate the methane production from slurry fermentation processes, *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 56 (2016) 603–610. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.11.093>.
- [101] J. Grahovac, A. Jokić, J. Dodić, D. Vučurović, S. Dodić, Modelling and prediction of bioethanol production from intermediates and byproduct of sugar beet processing using neural networks, *Renew. Energy*. 85 (2016) 953–958. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2015.07.054>.
- [102] S.O. Dahunsi, S. Oranusi, V.E. Efevbokhan, Optimization of pretreatment, process performance, mass and energy balance in the anaerobic digestion of *Arachis hypogaea* (Peanut) hull, *Energy Convers. Manag.* 139 (2017) 260–275. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2017.02.063>.
- [103] R. Kumar, G. Dhanarajan, D. Sarkar, R. Sen, Multi-fold enhancement in sustainable production of biomass, lipids and biodiesel from oleaginous yeast: An artificial neural network-genetic algorithm approach, *Sustain. Energy Fuels*. 4 (2020) 6075–6084. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0se00922a>.
- [104] V. V. Nair, H. Dhar, S. Kumar, A.K. Thalla, S. Mukherjee, J.W.C. Wong, Artificial neural network based modeling to evaluate methane yield from biogas in a laboratory-scale anaerobic bioreactor, *Bioresour. Technol.* 217 (2016) 90–99. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biortech.2016.03.046>.
- [105] B. Ozkaya, A. Demir, M.S. Bilgili, Neural network prediction model for the methane fraction in biogas from field-scale landfill bioreactors, *Environ. Model. Softw.* 22 (2007) 815–822. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2006.03.004>.
- [106] C. Waewsak, A. Nopharatana, P. Chaiprasert, Neural-fuzzy control system application for monitoring process response and control of anaerobic hybrid reactor in wastewater treatment and biogas production, *J. Environ. Sci.* 22 (2010) 1883–1890. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1001-0742\(09\)60334-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1001-0742(09)60334-X).
- [107] S.K. Behera, S.K. Meher, H.S. Park, Artificial neural network model for predicting methane percentage in biogas recovered from a landfill upon injection of liquid organic waste, *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy*. 17 (2015) 443–453. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-014-0798-4>.
- [108] F. Tufaner, Y. Avşar, M.T. Gönüllü, Modeling of biogas production from cattle manure with co-digestion of different organic wastes using an artificial neural network, *Clean Technol. Environ.*

- Policy. 19 (2017) 2255–2264. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-017-1413-2>.
- [109] F. Tufaner, Y. Demirci, Prediction of biogas production rate from anaerobic hybrid reactor by artificial neural network and nonlinear regressions models, *Clean Technol. Environ. Policy*. 22 (2020) 713–724. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10098-020-01816-z>.
- [110] H. Abu Qdais, K. Bani Hani, N. Shatnawi, Modeling and optimization of biogas production from a waste digester using artificial neural network and genetic algorithm, *Resour. Conserv. Recycl.* 54 (2010) 359–363. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2009.08.012>.
- [111] P. Holubar, L. Zani, M. Hager, W. Fr. oschl, Z. Radak, R. Braun, Advanced controlling of anaerobic digestion by means of hierarchical neural networks, *Water Res.* 36 (2002) 2582–2588. <http://www.utb-shop.de/autoren/babka-anna/gender-und-dekonstruktion-9267.html>.
- [112] Y. Shin, R. Smith, S. Hwang, Development of model predictive control system using an artificial neural network: A case study with a distillation column, *J. Clean. Prod.* 277 (2020) 124124. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.124124>.
- [113] M. Pirouti, J. Wu, J. Ekanayake, N. Jenkins, Dynamic modelling and control of a direct-combustion biomass CHP unit, *Proc. Univ. Power Eng. Conf.* (2010).
- [114] S. Safarian, C. Richter, R. Unnthorsson, Waste Biomass Gasification Simulation Using Aspen Plus: Performance Evaluation of Wood Chips, Sawdust and Mixed Paper Wastes, *J. Power Energy Eng.* 07 (2019) 12–30. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jpee.2019.76002>.
- [115] J. Yu, J.D. Smith, Validation and application of a kinetic model for biomass gasification simulation and optimization in updraft gasifiers, *Chem. Eng. Process. - Process Intensif.* 125 (2018) 214–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cep.2018.02.003>.
- [116] M. Göllles, S. Reiter, T. Brunner, N. Dourdoumas, I. Obernberger, Model based control of a small-scale biomass boiler, *Control Eng. Pract.* 22 (2014) 94–102. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conengprac.2013.09.012>.
- [117] R. Bauer, M. Göllles, T. Brunner, N. Dourdoumas, I. Obernberger, Modelling of grate combustion in a medium scale biomass furnace for control purposes, *Biomass and Bioenergy*. 34 (2010) 417–427. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biombioe.2009.12.005>.
- [118] R. Seeber, M. Göllles, N. Dourdoumas, M. Horn, Reference shaping for model-based control of biomass grate boilers, *Control Eng. Pract.* 82 (2019) 173–184. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.conengprac.2018.10.006>.
- [119] M. V. Americano Da Costa Fo, J.E. Normey-Rico, Modeling, control and optimization of ethanol fermentation process, *IFAC*, 44 (2011) 10609–10614. <https://doi.org/10.3182/20110828-6-IT-1002.02547>.
- [120] O. Paquet-Durand, S. Assawarajuwan, B. Hitzmann, Artificial neural network for bioprocess monitoring based on fluorescence measurements: Training without offline measurements, *Eng. Life Sci.* 17 (2017) 874–880. <https://doi.org/10.1002/elsc.201700044>.